

PEOPLE WITH MENTAL ILLNESS IN THE MAINSTREAM MUSLIM COMMUNITY: NARRATIVES FROM MAGUINDANAONS

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People with Mental Illness in the Mainstream Muslim Community: Narratives from Maguindanaons

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Abstract

This narrative study sought to discover the experiences of Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group regarding people with mental illness in the mainstream. There were nine (9) Muslim participants in this study selected using a purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique. The researcher provided a semi-structured interview questionnaire and thematic content analysis was used to analyze the results. Experiences of the community revealed four themes which are risk of aggression and violence, Unusual and off the wall actuations, wretchedness and abject despondency, and facts and myths on mental illness. Coping mechanisms revealed five themes which are strong faith in Allah, giving and seeking intervention and support, generosity of spirit, kindness and acceptance, and avoidance among this individual. Finally, participants' insight revealed themes such as lack of spiritual foundation to and faith in Allah, major stress and trauma in life, lack of appropriate treatment and mental health professionals, lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support. The need for mental health professionals, treatment facilities and psychoeducation in Muslim local community are strongly recommended to help community in dealing people suffering from mental illness.

Keywords: *mental illness, mainstream, Muslim community, Maguindanaons, narratives, thematic content analysis*

Introduction

Mental illness as defined in diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorder fifth edition (5th ed.; DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013) is a syndrome characterized by clinically significant disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotion regulation, or behavior. The nomenclature reflects dysfunction in the psychological, biological, or developmental processes underlying mental functioning. A Global statistics shows that there are about 300 million people which is equivalent to 4.4% of the world's population globally estimated affected by mental illness according to World Health Organization | Mental disorders (2015). In the Philippines, it was revealed that in 1.4 million individuals having disabilities, 14% are mentally disabled according to national census conducted last 2010 (Lally, Tully and Samaniego, 2019). Moreover, about 88 cases of mental health issues had found for every 100,000 Filipinos including Muslims according to Philippine Health Information System on Mental Health (PHIS-MH) as cited by Chrisa Ane Magtubo (2016) on article "Mental Health in the Philippines. Most of these cases are left untreated due to lack of sufficient mental health facilities and even mental health professionals in the vicinities leading them hover in the mainstream (WHO, 2014).

Despite of the prevailing cases on mental illness and its accompanied problems, there are still no universal agreement on the definition among mental health practitioners considering individual's beliefs, practices, and cultures (Butcher, Hooley & Mineka, 2016; Bulbulia and Laher, 2016). On the other hand, these cannot be ignored and served as significant role on how mental illness and people having it will be perceived by the society (Choudhry et.al, 2016; Ally and Laher, 2008). Muslim community (followers of Islam) around the world advocate supernatural forces such as witchcraft and possession (Uvais, 2017). The attributions are not unique to the community. In fact, the origin of idea can be traced among earlier origins of Buddhism, Hinduism, Pagaism, Wicca, Hatian voodoo, African traditionalism, Judaism and Christianity (Islam and Campbell, 2014). In addition, Qur'an which considered the holy bible of Muslims contributes to the views and perceptions among the community on mental illness. Such supernatural belief like the possession of Jinns is found in 27:163 and 55:15 of the holy Qur'an (Islam and Campbell, 2014). In non-western countries such as Philippines, Muslim people in the community rely on supernatural and religious factors. Thus, implementing the traditional indigenous healing such as exorcism (Alrawi, Fetters, Killawi, Hammad, & Padela, 2012).

There are several studies conducted in other countries among Muslims in relation to issues on mental illness however, only few and limited studies conducted in the Philippine context where Muslim community are also accessible. This gap or deficiencies by previous researchers would like to fill in by this study. Previous researchers suggested that there is an urgent need for further investigation in terms of specific culture (Choudhry et.al, 2016; Jones and Corrigan, 2012) and specific religious beliefs and practices (Wesselmann, 2010; Ally and Laher, 2007). These suggested that societal differences impact on how people views individual suffering from mental illness (Islam, Multani, Hynie, Shakya, & McKenzie, (2017). The complex interaction between these factors has not been explored and a need for more refined study is urgently needed. In addition, this research deserves attention among mental health practitioners and demand to strengthen the liaison between religious belief and mental health care in the community (Uvais, 2017).

Thus, the objective for this study is to unearth the experiences of Muslim community specifically the Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group in Maguindanao on people with mental illness. Specifically, the researcher wants to gain understanding on the experiences, coping mechanisms and insights of Muslim community among people having mental illness in the mainstream. Muslims are greatly influenced by religion and culture about their views and perception on mental illness. The phenomena are known to be universal that affects every society. Thus, uniqueness of this study among other studies is it will focus only on Muslim in the Philippine context specifically in Maguindanao province.

Research Questions

This study sought to explore the views and experiences of Muslim community regarding people with mental illness in the mainstream. The primary research question for this study is "What are the experiences of Muslim community specifically Maguindanaons among people with mental illness in the mainstream." Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the relevant experiences of the Maguidanaon community on people with mental illness?
2. What are the coping mechanisms of the Maguindanaon community in dealing with the challenges they faced among people having a mental illness in the mainstream?
3. What are the Insights of the Muslim community regarding their experience with people having a mental illness?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used qualitative research design in investigation. Qualitative method is an inquiry procedure involves understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that investigate an existing social or human pressing problem. The researcher builds a complex, holistic picture, analyzes words coming from participants, reports detailed views of them, and conducts the study in a natural setting (Creswell, 2013).

In the context of this study, the research utilized narrative research design, a type of qualitative research method. The researcher described the lives of individuals, collect and tell stories about people's lives, and write narratives of individual experiences (Connelly and Clandinin, 1990). This method allows an individual to narrate their personal experiences, and by asking one or more participants, the researcher can now provide stories. These stories are often retold by the one who interviewed a narrative chronology. This method combines participants' and researcher' s views and perceptions based on their life experiences in a collaborative narrative (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000).

Participants

The researcher interviewed nine (9) Maguindanaons ages 34 to 49 living in Maguindanao province, specifically Poblacion Pagalungan. According to Creswell (2014), 7 to 25 participants are sufficient for the qualitative approach. Specifically on his book "Qualitative Design", Creswell suggested that one (1) or two (2) participants are already acceptable for Narrative research design as long as data is already saturated. Out of nine (9) Maguindanaon participants, a total of five (5) underwent In-depth Interview (IDI) which according to Creswell (2014) is already a sufficient number of participants to get a rich or saturated data. For choosing the informants in in-depth interview, the researcher included participants who encountered people with mental illness to make sure that he can generate relevant data from the informants. Specifically, the researcher included Babo Pakong (faith healer), Bapa Rasul (Imaam), Bapa Tahir (teacher), Bapa Abdul (attorney) and Bapa Daud (medical doctor).

For focus group discussions (FGD), the remaining four (4) participants agreed to be interviewed by sharing their experiences with one another. The four participants were Babo Lambay (Muslim barangay leader), Babo Kuri (family member of a person suffers from mental illness), Babo Lanie and Babo Dido (bystanders). Guest, Namey and McKenna (2016) suggested that number of FGD participants (sample size) should be between 3-6 to identify 90% of themes.

The sampling design or method employed for both in-depth interview and FGD are the non-probability sampling technique, specifically, the researcher used a purposive sampling. A purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling is a sampling technique wherein the researcher selects a sample of participants based on the knowledge about the study (Creswell, 2014).

Inclusion criteria are those characteristics the prospective participants must have, and exclusion criteria are those characteristics that disqualify potential participants from inclusion in the study. For this paper, the researcher only includes nine (9) Maguindanaon participants ages 34 to 49 who already encounter people with mental illness, especially in the mainstream Muslim community, to generate relevant information (Creswell, 2014). Participants are bona fide residents of Poblacion Pagalungan, Maguindanao, a Muslim barangay leader, Imam (person who leads prayers in a mosque), and Faith healer, a doctor, teacher, lawyer, bystander and family (of a person with mental illness). For the exclusion, children under 18 years old, persons with mental illness or anyone who cannot consent for themselves, are excluded from this study to avoid ethical issues. In addition, participants who reside from poblacion but did not encounter people with mental illness are also excluded. The participant may feel discomfort during the interview because of the sensitive nature of the topic being studied. Thus, they may opt to withdraw to the study if they feel emotionally and psychologically distressed while the study is being conducted.

Procedure

Prior to the proper data collection, the researcher presented a title proposal to the panelist with the help of his adviser. After the title was approved, the researcher immediately applied for University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) certificate of approval (COA) to start the conduct of the study. All forms (Form A, B, C, D & E) were all secured to make sure that all necessary

study protocols are being executed during data gathering procedure.

During the actual data collection, the following systematic procedure is applied after securing the certificate of approval (COA) to conduct the study. First, the researcher sent a letter to Mayor Salik P. Mamasabulod of Población Pagalungan, Maguindanao, asking permission to interview with the community participants. After the letter has been approved, the researcher looks for potential participants in the community who encountered people with mental illness in the mainstream and are willing to be part of the study, meaning they must sign first the consent letter. This activity started last September 15, 2019 and it ended last on September 19, 2019, which is earlier than the expected date. Second, the researcher asked the participants to record the interview using a tape recorder and take down their responses, including verbal and nonverbal responses. The data needed for the study were collected through a semi-structured interview questionnaire; these are open-ended questions that lead the participants in giving elaborated answers on the different research questions. This also allows the researcher to have flexibility in questioning the participants using probing questions (Hunsley and Lee, 2009).

The interview took up for three (3) days because of the availability of the participants. The individual interview properly took for about a maximum of 25 to 30 minutes or until the data gathered is saturated for both in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). To make sure that the data needed are already enough and sufficient, the participants IDI and FGD have no time limit in answering the interview given them. In transcribing the recorded data, the researcher ensured that each word was verbatimly recorded and reviewed. Since the study participants are the Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group, the researcher translated all responses from Maguindanaon to English, which was validated by an English Professor who is a Maguindanaon. Using back translation, the researcher looks for another English professor who can translate the English version into the original language.

Then, he analyzed the results to be able to know what the participants mean for their answers. In addition, to ensure the dependability of the results, the researcher kept the raw recorded data for safety purposes, and just in case the panels of the study will be asking for evidence. The results drawn from this research study can be used to explain the Muslim community's experiences among people with mental illness in the mainstream. This also included their perception of mental illness, coping mechanisms, and insights. Conclusions and interpretations for this study were carefully analyzed to ensure that themes are reasonable, consistent, and distinct. In reaching the results, the researcher makes sure that he is equipped with sufficient knowledge of the process and how to analyze the data gathered.

After all chapters were all completed, the researcher presented the findings through public research forum with the theme "Inspiring Changes and Innovation in Education" held by the UM professional schools last December 11, 2020. All necessary comments and suggestions were all followed and finally presented to panel members during the final defense held last March 23, 2021 via zoom platform.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized a Colaizzi's method in analyzing his data. According to Turunen, Perälä, and Meriläinen (2011), Colaizzi's method consists of seven step by step procedures which implemented and discussed below: The first step done by the researcher is the preparation of all transcripts which was initially obtained from nine (9) Muslim participants. The recorded and transcribed statements from indepth interview (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD) interviews were read and reviewed for several times to make sure that it is verbatimly recoded. Second step done by the researcher was extracting the significant elements from each transcription after reviewing it for several times. Each significant responses or statements were extracted and written on a sheet of paper noting their transcription code: researchs questions and particular participants who answered it. Third step done by the researcher was the analysis of significant statements. Each meaning formulated was categorized, reflecting a comprehensive account. Fourth step was thematic clustering (core ideas) where all theme clusters were given and characterized with a unique theme or main theme. Fifth step was the consultation with an expert researcher to review all the data taken and confirming it as the exact description of the persoanal experiences of Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group among people with mental illness in the mainstream. Sixth step done was reviewing and polishing of the results by simply removing redundant words and vague information to make sure that only one final structure and clear information were included. That is to maintain the strength of the study. Finally, validation of the results is the most important step in this method. During this step, findings were returned discussed to the Muslim participants. This final step reflects whether the interview has been correctly captured and presented.

In the actual process of formulating themes based on the experiences, thematic content analysis was used to analyze the data, focusing and examining themes within the data, which emphasized systematic organization and sufficient description of the data set derived from the Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group (Babbie and Mouton, 2005). Moreover, the subjectivity of the responses is explored through the perceptions, feelings, and experiences that the participants shared. Thematic analysis is one that looks across all the data to identify the common issues that recur and identify the main themes that summarizes all the views the researcher collected. This is the common method for descriptive qualitative projects.

Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness refers to the scientific worth and credibility of a qualitative study (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). To ensure trustworthiness, Lincoln and Guba provide the following criteria: Credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Details and an explanation of each criterion are discussed below. Credibility refers to demonstrating that the research utilized rigorous methods, and

the data is interpreted and represented truthfully by the researcher (Polit and Beck, 2012; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Several ways were utilized during this study to assure rigor. For this study, prolonged engagement, data triangulation, peer analysis, and member checking were carried out to establish credibility. Triangulation was also employed in this study wherein triangulation is based on the premise that no single method can adequately solve the problem, and each method reveals different aspects of empirical data (Patton, 2002). Transferability refers to demonstrating that the findings are applicable in other settings (Polit and Beck, 2012; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). To address the transferability, a detailed description of the participants' experience was provided. Dependability and confirmability also were practiced in this study. Dependability refers to the consistency and reliability of the data over time and similar conditions (Polit and Beck, 2012). While confirmability refers to whether the data represents the participants' experience and not the researcher's own biases or personal point of view (Polit and Beck, 2012). Dependability was demonstrated by meeting and collaborating with the participants. This includes allowing them to read their narratives in this study to confirm that no changes or misinterpretation from the researcher will transpire. Moreover, confirmability was used by describing how conclusion and interpretation were established by providing direct examples from the data.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher provided ethical consideration for this study by implementing the following measures: UMERC review, voluntary participation, privacy and confidentiality, Informed consent process, recruitment, risks and benefits, biosafety and other ethical consideration such as plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, focus group participant identification, deceit, observation, permission from organization or location, technology issues and authorship.

University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee. The researcher underwent a thorough process to meet ethical standards implemented by the UMERC before the data collection. This includes the committee's different forms, such as form A, B, C, D, E, and other study protocol forms. In addition, all five validated questionnaires are included to ensure that the questions are not discriminating and will not impose any negative judgement.

Voluntary participation. The participation of this research is entirely voluntary. Informed consent was provided to make sure that the participants joined voluntarily during the data gathering procedure. In addition, participants may withdraw during the process, especially if they feel threatened with regard to the topic.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The researcher assured the participants that confidentiality is highly considered and will be highly observed. In conducting this study, everything that the participants stated are kept. Confidentiality of the identity of the participants (anonymity) is also guaranteed. Narratives and data collected will be kept safe and remained private. Furthermore, only the researcher and the mentor of this study have access to privacy. To address ethics requirements and confidentiality, codes are assigned to each of the participants. Pseudonyms are also used to hide the participants' authentic identities in this study to value and respect their involvement in this study's process. A collaborative relationship is established with the participants in the belief that this would help them become transparent and comfortable in disclosing their experiences, inner feelings, and thoughts. Lastly, the confidentiality and privacy of the records will be kept unless the law requests it, or if necessary, to protect the participant's rights and welfare.

Informed Consent Process. The freedom and right of the participants, whether to participate in this study was considered. Notification of the details, nature, and purpose of the study was given to the participants through informed consent. In the consent letter, a response section was provided to indicate participants' voluntary participation. Informed consent is a procedure processed by the researcher for participants to be fully informed about the study's nature and which potential respondents can freely choose to participate in the study. It provided enough information about the research to potential participants to give their informed consent (Apruebo, 2007). In addition, It will also give the potential participants to know who among them are willing to participate in the study. The researcher also informed them that he used audio-recorded while having an interview. Ample time was given to participants to let them discern their participation. The participants of this study are ensured in terms of privacy, and no personal data will be collected.

Texts from authors and researches that been used in any part of this research have been and fully referenced. The method for gathering data, specifically semi-structured interviews, does not contain any degrading, discriminating, or any other unacceptable language that could be offensive to any study participants. The interview for this study is designed to collect information directly related to the research questions, and no private or personal questions was asked from participants.

Recruitment. With the help of barangay leaders from the different areas of the municipality of Pagalungan, the researcher identified the right participants. This is to ensure the confidentiality and safety of the participants. In addition, participants who cannot read and/ or write due to illiteracy, especially in English, were provided a Maguidanaon translation of the informed consent. This is to make sure that they will fully understand the consent letter. Lastly, the researcher did not recruit participants who cannot give personal consent due to cultural factors, children under the age of 18, and those with mental illnesses or incapacities.

Risks. The researcher asked the participants to share some personal and confidential information. It was explained to the community that If they feel uncomfortable for any of the questions during the interview, they may opt not to answer the questions. No reason was asked for not responding in the interview. In addition, the researcher also explained that the participants might withdraw if he or she will feel distressed psychologically or emotionally.

Benefits. The potential benefits of participating in this study will help the community in understanding the current situation about mental health issues. By his/her participation, it can generate information which is helpful and can be used by government agencies such as mental health institution. Thus, this study can create a program that focuses on mental health education or awareness to improve the community.

Plagiarism. Any text from the different authors is properly cited and put in the reference area. Plagiarism check, such as Turnitin software is also provided to ensure that any texts in this paper were all properly cited and presented.

Fabrication. To avoid fabrication, the research makes sure that every statement cited from the different authors are properly examined its meaning to avoid the inappropriate conclusion. In addition, the study makes sure that all statements are consistent with the existing literature where it is originated.

Falsification. No claims were falsified just to fit its results to the existing theories, and the research will make sure that there will be no exaggerated claims.

Conflict of interest. To practice ethical consideration, the researcher makes sure that its primary objective is to unearth the community's experiences on people with mental illness, their coping mechanisms and insights only, and no traces of any secondary interest.

Focus Group Participant Identification. To avoid any disclosure of any confidential information given to the participants in the focus group discussion, the researcher provided informed them before the conduct of Focus Group Discussion. In addition, the informed consent signed by the participants contains the provisions that all information should be kept confidential.

Deceit. To meet the ethical consideration, the researcher assured that deception and overstatement about the purpose and objectives of this study are avoided. With this, the researcher makes sure to focus on what is speculated in the informed consent. This includes the nature of the study, its benefits, and its possible risks that the participants may encounter. Hereafter, any type of communication concerning the research was done with honesty and transparency.

Permission from Organization/Location. A letter to conduct was provided by the researcher to the Municipal mayor Salik P. Mamasabulod. The Dean approved this letter of professional school, Dr. Eugenio S. Guhao, and the researcher's adviser Dr. Ronadora E. Deala.

Storage and Disposal. For the safety of data gathered, proper storage and disposal were observed in the entire research process. The researcher will be retained the data until there is no reasonable possibility required to defend the paper against allegations of scientific misconduct and future or subsequent studies. This is possible because the researcher also indicated this in the participants' consent form to which the participants agreed. However, should the data need to be destroyed, the researcher shall remember to protect the participants' confidentiality throughout the process. Paper records will be shredded instead of carelessly tossing it in the garbage. In addition, all records stored on a computer hard drive will be erased to remove all data from the storage device.

Authorship. The researcher cited an authorship contribution statement and acknowledged the contribution of all the people who helped in the Acknowledgment section of this paper, from his research adviser, research panelist during proposal and in final defense, UMER, validators, reviewers, data analyst, grammarian of this study and other significant individuals who inspired the researcher during his research endeavor.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the various themes derived from the different stories of Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group regarding their experiences among people with mental illness in the mainstream. This chapter includes themes under challenges, coping mechanisms and their insights among these people. The themes were drawn from the information gathered through in-depth interviews and focus-group discussions (FGD). In-depth interviews (IDI) and FGD were conducted to gain understanding, insights, and to answer the research questions. For confidentiality purposes, the researcher utilized "code names" to protect the participants' identity and exercise the anonymity as stipulated in APA ethical guidelines.

During the data gathering procedure, specifically in the interview sessions, all participants from individual interview to focus-group-discussions were given the same and exact questions. These questions were validated and evaluated by different professionals to make sure that all questions do not contain any negative dictions which might affect the participants psychologically or emotionally. In addition, Maguindanaon version of the tool was provided. The tool was validated by a Maguindanaon university professor. In addition, all participants were asked to speak in their most comfortable language or dialect during the interview proper.

For the individual interview, the researcher included five (5) Maguindanaon participants - a medical doctor, a lawyer, a teacher, an Imam, and a faith healer who have first-hand encounter with people suffering from mental illness. For the focus-group discussion, the researcher included two (2) bystanders, one (1) barangay official of Barangay Damalask, and one (1) family member of a person having mental illness. Overall, the researcher had nine (9) participants which according to Creswell (2014), are already sufficient especially if data is already saturated: five (5) individual in-depth interview and four (4) FGD participants. The interview was conducted and took long for about three (3) consecutive days and was conducted at barangay Damalask Pagalungan, Maguindanao with the permission

of the municipal mayor Salik P. Mamasabulod and with the assistance of the barangay captain. Finally, the researcher used a tape recorder and notebook to record the discussions including both verbal and non-verbal cues for both individual and FGD as suggested by Gee (2014).

Categorization of Data

As soon as the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion were all accomplished, the audio-tape record was transcribed in verbatim, translated and analyzed.

During the formal data analysis, three steps were undertaken. The first step was data reduction in which the data extracted from the transcriptions were chosen, cut down and organized using the thematic content analysis table. The next step was data display in which the researcher presented the data containing the participants primary personal information, core ideas, and major themes as shown in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. In categorizing the data, all generated themes were presented according to their corresponding research questions. Opposite the major themes in the table were the core ideas from the responses of the Maguindanaon participants. The third step involved drawing conclusions and verification. At this point of the study, according to Gonzalez (2016), the preliminary ideas and patterns about the results or findings are developed. In presenting the results, the researcher included the verbatim statements in italics citing the participants code names followed by English translations provided after each statement.

Table 1. Participants' Information

<i>Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Profession</i>	<i>Location (Province)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Educational Background</i>	<i>Study Group</i>
Bapa Daud (P9)	Doctor	Maguindanao	46	Medical doctor	In-depth Interview
Bapa Abdul (P8)	Attorney	Maguindanao	34	College Graduate	In-depth Interview
Bapa Tahir(P7)	Teacher	Maguindanao	49	Doctorate	In-depth Interview
Bapa Rasul (P6)	Imam	Maguindanao	48	College level	In-depth Interview
Babo Pakong (P5)	Faith Healer	Maguindanao	46	Elementary level	In-depth Interview
Babo Lambay (P1)	Brgy. Captain	Maguindanao	49	High school level	Focus Group
Babo Kuri (P2)	Family member	Maguindanao	45	High school graduate	Focus Group
Babo Lanie (P3)	Bystander 1	Maguindanao	42	Elementary level	Focus Group
Babo Dido (P4)	Bystander 2	Maguindanao	40	Elementary level	Focus Group

The table 1 above shows the basic information only of the participants indicating the primary identifying elements of their identity. Overall, the researcher was able to interview five (5) individuals for in-depth interview and four (4) individuals focus-group discussion with the total of nine participants from Barangay Damalask Pagalungan, Maguindanao. All responses from the research participants were recorded using audio-tape recorders which later on were transcribed, analyzed, coded, and categorized as basis for analysis as suggested steps in Collaizi method (Goirgi, 1978).

Relevant Experiences of Maguindanaon Community on People with Mental Illness in the Mainstream

All themes derived from the interviews of the participants were carefully examined and categorized. In the data analysis, the researcher was able to formulate codes for the first research objective which goes in the notion of; What are relevant experiences of Maguindanaon community on people with mental illness in the mainstream? It showed that these vital components correspond greatly to the inquiry, thus it was seen as the following: risk of aggression and violence, unusual and off the wall actuations, wretchedness and abject dependency, and facts and myths on mental illness.

Risk of aggression and violence. In terms of relevant experiences of the community among people having mental illness in the mainstream, most participants answered negative experience which themed as risk of aggression and violence brought about by these individuals. Similarly, the participants in the focus group discussion also mentioned negative experience as their response as a struggle. During the interview, the researcher asked the FGD participants on their personal experience about people having mental illness in the mainstream. Most of the participants laughed, in fact, they mentioned one particular individual in the community named "Dutin" or "Parengkoy", a 28-year old male whom the researcher also encountered during the three-day interview at Barangay Damalask, Pagalungan, Maguindanao. The researcher described "Dutin" or "Parengkoy" as neat and clean person despite his mental health condition. According to the narratives of the participants on FGD, "Dutin" was a victim of drug use and drug addiction. Seven years ago, "Dutin" was sent by his mother to Manila to study for college. He was described by participants like Babo Kuri, Babo Lambay and Babo Lanie as a smart and very kind person then, he in fact excel in school way back. Eventually, because of the influence of his peers, he engaged himself into prohibited drug resulting to developed mental illness in Manila. Due to his condition, his mother was forced to send him back to Barangay Damalask and since she cannot sustain Dutin financially, her mother decided to leave him hover in the mainstream.

Because of this, Babo Kuri a 45-year-old mother of 3 children took him in and cared for Dutin; she also helped him build his own shelter. Since Dutin is mentally unstable, there are a lot of negative experiences the community have faced. One of the common struggles of the community with Dutin was whenever he relapses, he gets out of control on his behavior and become violent & aggressive. According to Babo Kuri, he is capable of hurting people, keeps on throwing anything he gets in his hands, he punches and spans anyone when he feels irritable and as a result, people had to hide and avoid him including Babo Kuri for safety. This was

confirmed also by Babo Lanie, a neighbor, and Babo Lambay, a barangay official of Damalask who are in the same neighborhood with Dutin. Below are statements of Babo Kuri and Babo Lanie on their experience:

...Mikaw kandauma namba a kapegkabunegen buba anan a pedtaka kami pamagena ka eh pamengel sa mga walay. Eehhnnn, nana di moman mapakay eh samaytoa ah engila-gilan nenka sekanin ka panuntok, pametay.. na langon na nyabay a pamantay nen. Ahnn so mga walay manem mikaw magabi, na pamantay nen ba mga walay ba oh magabi. Nanba eh pakagelk samana sa lekanin . na tuba, mikaw magutem, maya andu tupan ka endadakaw sambay ka embabaliba, na mamanaty sekanin, na nanba ka ingate Kaden ka di kaa kemuana sa tuba ka sigu sigu a benal a kasakitan kanin. Pamangenggelk sekanin sa panimbaw, pamengel sa mga wato ba basta enda pan e ka'ami nen lon... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q1)

...he throws anything including stones and anything he gets in hand. We never try to make any jokes on his condition because he might punch you, spank you, everything inside the house, he throws it. Every night, he keeps on throwing anything. That is why people here are afraid and avoid him. Every time he relapses, for sure he can really hurt you...

...uway! na panuntok sa mga mga tao ba anya...(Babo Pakong) ... (m4a_P5_Q1)

...Agree, he actually punches anyone...

Babo Pakong a faith healer who is a resident of Barangay Damalask also narrated her negative experience brought about by these individuals having mental illness hovering in the mainstream. According to Babo Pakong, she fears these individuals because of their capacity to hurt anyone. According to her, these people display physically threatening behavior such as throwing objects at people. Babo Pakong shared her personal experience with her neighbor named "Pia", who has mental illness also like Dutin. The community believed that "Pia" became mentally ill due to personal reason, her separation from her husband whom she obsessed with. According to Babo Pakong, "Pia" displays aggressive and violent actions like for instance spanking her father while praying in their house believing that her parents, specially her father, hid her husband. Below is her statement:

...nagilekan mambo, ka pamengel sekanin sa mga watu...tuba pagiwasan namu... Sakabyas bun, mana dili den kaulian, malgek eh kambabangala nen, andu pakagelk ka pamantay sa wato, ando di ka makajoke... si babo nani di ged makatug ka pedsendetan nen sekanin eh napambelag sa lekanilan na si ama nen andu si ina nen. pembetay nen e tuba si ama nen ah ah nakametal tangka...binetay nin si ama nin sa begkubong , na dala makadsambayang ka pedu den ged eh tengu nen. Megkagem.. uway, pinatulog nyan den maenm kadii pakatulog. Hahahahahah panald..guna so nakapila gay den e makatug den ka menggamot mabu e enenggay nelan nun so kinauli nyan. (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q1)

...first in my mind? it's really fear, because this person most of the time is throwing anything gets in hand such as stones... They are different and I feel threatened because they throw you stones...her parents cannot sleep well because she keeps on blaming her parents with what happened to her and her husband... she spansks her father while praying in their house. In fact, she became more and more aggressive.

Bapa Daud, who is the municipal doctor of Poblacion Pagalungan expresses also that he avoids people with mental illness in the mainstream not to discriminate but for the reason that he may get hurt specially these people at times are ferocious and aggressive. Similar problem also was encountered by other participants like Bapa Abdul, Bapa Rasul, and Bapa Tahir which according to them, these individuals suffering from mental illness are violent and capable of hurting other people.

Bapa Tahir, a teacher by profession added that they have a neighbor who was kept and tied in to prevent this person from going outside. He is also capable of hurting not just the other people but also even his own parents. Below are the statements gathered from the participants on their negative experience among people having mental illness in the mainstream:

...At times, they are violent, therefore I need to avoid them just to protect myself ahmmmm..nagalit minsan sa relatives ng tao na to kasi bakit hinayaan nila palaboy-2x kamag-anak nila...so nakakafeel minsan ng guilt sa side ng relatives nya....(Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

...At times, they are violent, therefore I need to avoid them just to protect myself. I am disappointed for the relatives of these individual because why they allow their relative to be in the mainstream?...

...people having this illness are at times violent, they are capable of hurting other people especially when they are attacked by their violent behavior... nya bay..madakel ged sa apya anda den mansamana...(Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q1)

... people having this illness are at times violent, they are capable of hurting other people especially when they are attacked by their violent behavior...in each of this places, we can actually see them in the mainstream...

...dahil ito ay nananakit. pati parents nya kaya nyang saktan. basta bayonte sya basta sinusumpong ng situatiion na yun. nambabato, kung ano mahawakan nya pwede nyang ipalo, then.wala narin sya pakialam kung nagsusuot pa na ito ng damit or wala. yun yung isa sa reason bakit sya hindi na pinapalabas ng bahay...(Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q1)

...because he is already violent, even his parents, he hurts them. He is violent every time he is triggered by the situation. Everything that he holds, he throws it to people...

Unusual and off the wall actuations. This theme was formulated when the participants answered items pertaining to activities done by these individuals that are considered less or non-threatening for them. However, they are uncommon and strange actions compared to what is considered normal and usual in the community. Some of these actuations which are experienced by the participants among people having mental illness are: displaying no proper hygiene, restless and anxious, talking to self, acts weird or does weird things, whispers to self, talks excessively, and incessantly, keeps picking trashes, does not sleep at night and wander around, laughs alone, keeps on running and laughing, and defecates in the room.

Bapa Tahir and Bapa Daud agreed that people with mental illness they have encountered in the mainstream have no proper hygiene. In fact, Bapa Tahir have encountered people having mental illness who are kept inside one room where he also defecates. Because the parents fear their son, they just give him food to eat and give him a bath by splashing water with a hose. It is challenging for the family since they cannot maintain the hygiene of their son due to unpredictable behavior.

In addition, Babo Lanie also said that this individual keeps on picking wastes anywhere for no apparent reason. Some statements from the participants below talks about the idea of no proper hygiene which are considered unusual:

... unang-una icocompare natin sila sa mga normal na tao, nagkakaroon sila ng mga hindi pangkaraniwan na actuations, katulad ng nagiging loner na o ginaisolate nila ang kanilang sarili, umiiwas sa tao, nagiging tulala minsan, at saka yung hygiene kung titignan natin, parang nakakaligtaan na yung kanilang physical. na itsura tulad ng kalinisan, pananamit, buhok, at saka yung pang araw2x na part ng hygiene ng tao. (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q1)

...First of all, if we compare them to those normal people, they have extraordinary actuations, like being loner, they isolate themselves, avoiding people, daydreaming, no proper hygiene like neatness, clothing, hair, and every hygiene...

...seeing things that cannot seen by normal people, talking to the self alone, no proper hygiene, palaboy-laboy na walang saplot, distress and different from others, I mean kakaiba behavior pinakakita nyaa...Ahmm they are distressed, no proper hygiene, magulo ang buhok.... usually schizophrenia kasi nasa mainstream talaga... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

...seeing things that cannot seen by normal people, talking to the self alone, no proper hygiene, walking in the mainstream without clothing, distress and different from others, I mean they shows bizarre behavior...They are distressed, no proper hygiene, hair are disorganized...usually people with schizophrenia are those really in the mainstream...

...buneg den a benal enan ka pamanggit den sa mga eh pamundot sa mga basura hahah. Pamundot enan sa mga basura... ma embabaliba. Ehh pedtalu2x sad ala kaped nin (laughing)... (Babo Lanie) (m4a_P3_Q3)

...She is really insane because she keeps on picking trashes... Keeps on talking to himself...

Babo Pakong has observed that this individual does weird things such as if whispering to someone who seems to be imperceptible. Based on the story of Babo Pakong, there are nights when they cannot sleep well because Pia, their neighborhood who suffers from mental illness would keep on walking around at night believing that her parents are hiding her husband somewhere. As a result, she would enter and trespass houses in her neighborhood believing that her husband is hidden in one of the houses. This makes the community including Babo Pakong feel threatened and the neighborhood is unable to sleep at night. Babo Lambay who is the Barangay captain, Babo Lanie, Babo Kuri, and Bapa Tahir also agreed on this experience among these people with mental illness. According to them:

...Aden ato na na eh pedtagedteb sa kena husto...si babo nani di ged makatug ka pedsendetan nen sekanin eh napambelag sa lekanilan na si ama nen andu si ina nen. pembetay nen e tuba si ama nen ah ah nakametal tangka...hen tuba e kigkapy na ehnen ka sabap ka tuba di pakatulog uman magabi..pelakaw-lakaw..tuba i mapatulog pilakaw-lakaw sekanin. panald.....so sa mga kawalayn na.. epangegkan nen tuba so mga balgkas ka tinago kumba lu ba si kaluma nen ah sa luma sa ludep ah... di mkatulog eto sumla etong taw ka di makatulog nan a tuba makwana den... (m4a_P5_Q1)

...they keep on whispering, and talking excessively...and yes, that's the reason she can't sleep, keeps on walking in the middle of the night, some of us neighborhood also is afraid for her. She believed that her parents hide her husband anywhere...Babo, who is also our neighborhood. her parents cannot sleep well because she keeps on blaming her parents for their separation with her husband...a lot of us neighborhood cannot sleep because, she might get enter in every house in the middle of the night...

...di pedtugen ka pelalakaw sya bai sa mga pamageltan a walai ah... (Babo Lambay) (m4a_P1_Q1)

...He cannot sleep actually every night and keeps on walking everywhere...

...uway, endaguy, andu edtatawa mon temegel...(Babo Lanie)

...She keeps on running and always laughing...(m4a_P3_Q1)

...Di ged kapanan. uway, nanba e kwana nen sakit nen di talaga lemenek... aahhn mapya magabi a dili pedtug... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q1)

...Does werd thinks, Yes, that's true, he seems to be restless and feeling anxious... yes, that's true, he can't really sleep...

...kasi usually natutulong ang karamihan, ito sila ay gising na gising. ah nagbabago yung pattern ng tulog nila, at saka even yung mga interest nila parang naghshishift. nakakaligtan na yung dating mga hobbies nila, they shifted to other hobbies na di na ahh considered na normal. na dati nilang ginagawa... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q1)

... While people are sleeping, they are wide awake. Changes in the pattern of sleep, they already forgot their hobbies, they shifted to another hobbies that is normal before...

Bapa Rasul, Bapa Abdul and Babo Pakong shared their experience on observed unusual and off the wall actuation of these individuals, aside from inappropriate behavior, another observation is also on the behavioral and physical aspect of these individuals. Their behavior occasionally get out of control however still considered less threatening.

According to their statements:

...Kung tingnan po natin kasi kung di normal yan halimbawa nagkausap kayo ay parang tumatawa kahit hndi dapat tatawanan yan tumatawa sya yung ang mga symptoms.nag-iba kasi hndi ganun ang dati nyang ginagawa...(Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q1)

...If you observed them, if it is an abnormal person for example, you are having conversation, they laugh even though the topic is actually a serious topic. It changes because way back, he or she is not like that...

...sa mamba ehh kabpas nen a nan? Masukwana nan bay? Nana ehhh kagya sakabiyas man ka aden ato n edtatawa, aden anto ah embityala sa dala kaped nen na na madtalu ta bun eh mana kabuneg bun samana...(m4a_P5_Q1)

...with his condition? I feel he is weird, he laughs at things, talking alone, when can really say he is insane...

...kumbaga naaout of control sya sa behavior nya...hndi nacontrol ng kanyang sarili, talagang medyo suspicious sya halimbawa yung mag asawa, minsan ay pinagbentangan kanyang asawa ay parang mayroon kang kasama ganon po yun po dahil yung ang ibang dahilan nagdvorse ang tao kasi yung utak nya nasisira...(Bapa Rasul)l (m4a_P6_Q3)

...they become out of control in their behavior, they cannot control themselves, really a suspicious, for example he or she keeps on accusing husband of having someone, something like that, that is why tendency is they will get divorced because the mind is already defective...

Wretchedness and abject despondency. Unhappiness and hopelessness were factors seen by Maguindanaon community that causes people to suffer from mental illness. This theme was formulated after the careful examining of participants statements. For example, Bapa Tahir who is a teacher and a Dean of college of Education (University of Southern Mindanao) narrated that he had an experience with his student during the first week of his class last June 2019. This student of him attempted to commit suicide by trying to hang herself using a rope inside her boarding house particularly inside the comfort room. The plan was unsuccessful since the student's roommate noticed and heard some strange commotion inside the comfort room. It was traumatic for the roommate, in fact, Bapa Tahir's attention was called and he suggested to the two students to seek a university guidance counselor for a help. It was still traumatic to Bapa Tahir although it was the third time to witness such situation.

Prior to the suicide attempt of the student, according to Bapa Tahir, he already noticed some behavioral changes in his student as a result of her depression. According to Bapa Tahir, his student kept on isolating herself inside the classroom, she preferred to be alone, and in terms of physical appearance, she had noticeable with lack of proper hygiene. This made Bapa Tahir wonder about the student's situation. Bapa Tahir said:

...Ito nagyare during the first week of this first semester. Ahh na kung saan eto na studyante ah nabalitaan po naming na ah nag attempt sya na magkakaroon ng suicide sa pamamagitan ng pagtatali, ah itinali nya yung kanyang...pagbibigti na kung san sya ay natangpuan sa comfort room ng kanilang boarding house...(Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q1)

...This happens during first week of the semester. Ahh wherein this student has already the history of attempting suicide through the use of rope. She hangs herself found in the comfort room inside their boarding house...

...unang-una icompare natin sila sa mga normal na tao, nagkakaroon sila ng mga hndi pangkaraniwan na actuations, katulad ng nagiging loner na o ginaisolate nila ang kanilang sarili, umiiwas sa tao, nagiging tulala minsan, at saka yung hygiene kung titignan natin, parang nakakaligtan na yung kanilang physical. na itsura tulad ng kalinisan, pananamit, buhok, at saka yung pang araw2x na part ng hygiene ng tao... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q1)

...First of all, if we compare them to those normal people, they have extraordinary actuations, like being loner, they isolate themselves, avoiding people, daydreaming, no proper hygiene like neatness, clothing, hair, and every hygiene...

Similarly, Bapa Abdul also told that people having mental illness tend to isolate themselves, notably no proper hygiene and they usually stay up late at night. According to Bapa Abdul, he also has personal experience with his neighbor named "Grace", a 62-years-old woman who developed mental illness due to psycho-emotional factor when her children abandoned her for the sole reason that they differ in religion, she was a catholic, she was left alone and she eventually lived by herself. Living alone, she developed and exhibit

negative emotions, she kept on over thinking, do not want to talk with. According to Bapa Abdul, it probably was caused by family problems and major stress causes her to feel down, unhappy and eventually led her to mental illness. Bapa Abdul said:

...symptoms,,ahhmm siguro yung tao na mayroon ng sakit sa utak talaga, ahmm tulala sa pagoverthink,, di ged pembibityala sa kaped, di ged bagayos sa kambalengga nen, di ged makatulog...For me, one reason was..pag mikaw nasuran na problema, subrang stress and down na sya masyadong sa daming problema nanba eh pakadsakit sa utek naa tao...(Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

...Symptoms, I think, people who are really having mental illness they over thinks negatively, tends to be alone, no proper hygiene, with sleep disturbances...For me, one reason was when we are bombarded with many problems, too much stress, down and unhappy because of many problems these are reasons for mental illness...

Babo Pakong who is a faith healer in the community also asserted and believed that mental illness was caused by too much loneliness of a person which could resulted into other minor physical symptoms such as frequent headache. This can also resulted into appetite disturbances which eventually turned to be mental illness. Babo Pakong said that:

...Ngen pan: pekakasakit ba eh ulo nen..., di pakakan sa mapya. malate sa kakan.na sya pebpawang sa ulo. naegkakasakit den so ulo. egkakasakit eh utek nin. andu malidu eh ginawa nin nan a egkasakit bun e ulo nin. sabap sa lu ba eh kalidu nu ginawa anto na lu ba pebawang sa ulo ah. kalidu na ginawa nen... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q3)

...what else, a person too much loneliness, this loneliness can cause many physical problem such as frequent experience of headaches and also individual with this condition resulted into appetite disturbances which lead him or her into many problems...

Some participants say that once you have mental illness such as depression, then, it cannot be treated already. Specially, if the case is already worst and it has been left untreated for a long period of time. This will result into inappropriate behavior such as disorganization of the actions and often indifferent about what the other people might find normal. Below are statements Babo Pakong, Babo Kuri, and Bapa Abdul about loneliness, hopelessness and helplessness experienced by these people:

...Sakabyas bun, mana dili den kaulian, malgek eh kambabangala nen, andu pakagelk ka pamantay sa wato, ando di ka makajoke.....na tuba pegkwanan pan ka pagawa sa balgkas, na babae pan manem... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q3)

...They are different, I think they cannot be treated already, they have dirty clothes, and I feel threatened because they will throw you stones and also, we cannot make jokes to them.....yes, she wants always to be naked also. and times doing exhibition like back tumbling...

...aden pan anan pelakaw-lakaw sa kalsada ah pag-envelop, dala nengkawn, aden anto ah kasagaran papageran bun...(Babu Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q1)

There are some who keeps on walking on the street holding an envelope. She does not care about people around her...

.....ahhmm siguro di na naliligo, nakakatakot kunti, nakakalimotan magdamit, wala ng pAkilam sa sarili niya, sira-sira ang buhok...ano pa ba..ahmmm maso tulala sekanin parati mambo. Dili ged embibityala sa tao. Sakabyas bun eh enggulan nin mikaw icompare nengka sa normal bun a taw... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

...ahhmm I think they don't take a bath, scary a bit, forgot to dress up, indifferent with his or herself, disorganized hair, very different compared to normal being...

Facts and Myths on Mental Illness. The final emerging theme drawn based on the participants' belief on mental illness is the myth and the facts about mental illness. Facts including the statements of participants that major reasons developing mental illness was brought about by the excessive use of illegal drugs such as "Shabu". Another fact told was that mental illness is genetically inherited, also it could be caused by stress and too much loneliness. These factors were believed to be the major source of mental illness. In terms of myth, participants asserted that mental illness is caused by the following including disobedience to Allah S.A.W, "Jinns" and "Deping" possession, and excessive unusual headache which are some examples mentioned during the interview session.

Bapa Daud, Bapa Tahir and Babo Lanie agreed and stated that the major cause of mental illness was due to stressful environment, genetics, and any alterations of the physiology of an individuals suffering from mental illness.

Bapa Daud who is a medical doctor mentioned that some of the reasons why people develop mental illness are, because of their stressful environment including but not limited to people around the individuals. Biological and genetic make up also plays important role in developing the illness since according to Bapa Daud mental illness can be dormant which can be triggered by an individual's stressful environment. Below is the statement of Bapa Daud:

...stressful environment, not so supportive people around us, biological cause and also can be like genetic factors...dala na kumbaga muli lang ginising ng experience at environment niya ang illness. Para siyang cancer, people who are having family history of cancer are more likely to develop it depending on his lifestyle...ahmm person who acquired mental illness. This are people who are also just like us, pero dahil sa traumatic experience sa buhay, and also may mga genetic composition din na involved, nag-karoon sila nitong tinatawag na mental disorder... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

...stressful environment, not so supportive people around us, biological cause and also can be like genetic factors...already there and triggered by the experiences and environment. It' like a cancer, people who are having family history of cancer are more likely to develop it depending on his lifestyle...ahmm person who acquired mental illness. This are people who are also just like us, but because of traumatic experiences in their life, and also there is genetic composition involved, they developed this what we called mental disorder...

Similarly, Bapa Tahir mentioned that mental illness runs in the family, it can be inherit from the parents or it can also be caused by individual's traumatic life experiences which according to Bapa may stem in the family or in the community itself. This was supported by the statement of Babo Lanie on the FGD group. Below are their statements:

...Sa na- observation ko as my perception, ito mga mental illness ay nag uugat ito sa mas malalim siguro na problema ah or maari naman itong siguro kung scientific naman, nakikita natin na nasa hereditary, or my history sa family pero kung iset aside natin ang yung sa hereditary, siguro nag uugat to sa mas malalim na trauma sa buhay or experiences nila na kanilang naencounter sa kanilang komunidad or sa pamilya mismo. Ahh... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

...Based on my observation, and as for my perception, mental illness stems from a intensive problems, or might be if it is scientific one, we can see that it is hereditary, or having the history in the family. However, if we set aside the heredity, I think it stems from a intensive trauma in life or experiences that they encounter in their community or in the family...

...aden andto ka nait then sa kapenggemaw nin. Nanba eh malgen den ah kait sa kapenggemaw nin... (Babo Lanie) (m4a_P3_Q1)

...At times, they are inherited form birth. In that case, it is impossible to treat this people...

In addition, Babo Kuri, Bapa Rasul, Babo Dido, believed that causes of mental illness were due to the excessive drug use brought about by the influence of peers. Like the case of Dutin or Parengkoy, who was influenced by his friends when he moved to study in the city; he was forced to take Illicit by his friends. In addition, Pia who also suffered from mental illness was believe influenced by her friends, according to participants, she took drugs injected on her body. She eventually became a drug dependent, she was even addicted to it when she came back to her family as she was influenced again since her father was also an illegal drug user. This illegal drug addiction led to brain dysfunction developing into mental illness. These were the statements of the participants:

...kagina kimwana den sa lugo nin anan and sa utek... (Babo Dido) (m4a_P4_Q3)

...Because drugs are already on his blood and brain...

...Agayd a kena bun man pagenda si bapa Tagikan... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q1)

...However, her father Tagikan is still using drugs...

...Medyo, parang madakel den...ganoon po, in fact, most of them are product of illegal drugs...which resulted in this condition...(Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q1)

...somehow, so far there are a lot of them now, in fact, most of them are product of illegal drugs...which resulted in this condition...

Major myths that emerged based on the participants narratives are the disobedience to God, excessive headaches, Jinns and Deping possession were notable among the responses. Babo Kuri believed that the condition of Dutin was a will of God and not solely his own choice. Babu Kuri said that:

...kagina tu den bag una e kinahanda nu kadenan guna salkanin, na tupan ka makasya sa lilaw na donya, nan a makwana sekanin,kakwanan na kapagitung kasalanan na kapagitong. ugayd a nani ah eh sekanin ah aden anto enan a naumba ni kinakwana kahnda no kadenan bun salkanin na marupng-dupang bun enan sekanin ka eh...dan ta pan ka kena dala enan gamit sa kwana na kena bun sekanin marupang-dupang ka nanba edtalon a mama ah eh college enan sekanin na mapya a benal eh..ehhn..nait na kinambarkada nin. agayd na basi naumban eh edtalun nu mga ustads na kadir nen ah mabuneg bun na sekanin ka upama ka bagi nin, na mapagitong nin eh di ako gemamit sa nyay ka marupang-dupang ako na...uagyd nanun ba eh kader nin a mabuneg bun ba sekanin...(Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q3)

...i think it is the will of Allah. Without any apparent reason for developing the illness, then it's really the will of God. His condition was given by Allah, that is to become mentally ill. Any person who develop mental illness without drug usage are all because of the will of God. Did you know that this person way back was already sent to college and I tell you, he is intelligent? However, he was influenced by his friends...

...uway2x entuba nanba eh mga ukit nin upama a eluba enan salkanin na maya namba maya so dili kadsambayang sa mosque. maya epegkagilk nin so kadenan na maya namulkan no kadenan ka maya ka man ba enan salkanilan na mga ustads...(Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q3)

...Yes, according to them. They reason for that is they do not visited Mosque and pray. They said that person is afraid to Allah, and because he was punished by God...

The reason for this condition is due to disobedience to Allah. This was supported by Bapa Rasul and Bapa Tahir. Disobeying Allah led people to develop the illness. This disobedience is characterized by not going to Mosque or Muslim Church, they do not submit themselves to Allah and no spiritual foundation. Most participants agreed on the core belief that every Muslim individual should submit himself and should always pray to Allah to strengthen faith and to avoid any forms of illnesses. Bapa Rasul and Bapa Tahir believed that an individual develop mental illness because of absence of prayer, and regain strength of faith, one must submit and surrender himself to Allah. He also suggested that one must read Qur'an (Holy Muslim Bible) in order to understand, cure or heal any diseases such as mental illness. Below is the statement of Bapa Rasul and Bapa Tahir on disobedience:

...mana sya sa laki, I think, another cause is when you try to be disobeyed Allah...its actually will of god to punish you for not visiting Mosque to pray...nanun bamambu... ..Maya inya po, in fact, sa Islam ay may kasabihan si abu allah maududi, " naka saad sa qur'an lahat ng tanong ng tao, masasagot sa qur'an na ito...eto rin ang sagot andu makagamot para mawala ang mga sakit kasama na ang sakit ng isang tao sa utak" ... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q1)

...In my own views, I think, another cause is when you try to be disobeyed Allah...its actually will of god to punish you for not visiting Mosque to pray...I think that's the reason also...It's like this, in fact, Islam has saying in Qur'an, all questions of humanity, they can be answered in Qur'an, this is also the answer to heal or cure all diseases including mental illness...

...sa spiritual na aspeto naman, kasi ang pinakafoundation dun yung ah strong foundation natin sa paniniala sa dioys na walang illness na hindi pwedeng magamot sa tulong o intervention ng ating panginoon. So ang pinaka basic doon siguro na kanilang pananao is pagpapatibay ng ating spiritual na paniwala. Na kahit anong mangyare, bastat strong ang foundation ng spiritual foundation natin, ah maconquer natin kung ano man mga problema na maging cause ng ganitong illness... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

...In spiritual aspect, the very foundation on that is the foundation or belief in God, that no illnesses can be cured without the help or intervention of God. So, the basic there I think is the perception is strengthening our spiritual belief. That whatever your situations are, for as long as you have a strong foundation, of spiritual foundation, then we can conquer all these problems that can cause this illness...

Bapa Abdul supported the statements of Babo Kuri, Bapa Rasul and Tahir and he added that disobedience to Allah which characterized by weak faith and foundation to God can resulted in developing mental illness which formed punishment by Allah. Below is the statement of Bapa Abdul:

...tpos samin naniniwala kasi kami na pag hindi ka ng mosque or sumamba kay Allah (SWA), parang punishment yan samin...satin pala according to Qur'an, muslim ka rin pala datu hahah....(laughing). Dahil ang sugo ni allah, kailangan syang sambahin para walang sakit na tumalab sayo, kasama na diyang ang sakit sa utak ng tao...kumbaga weak ang faith and foundation mo... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

... then in our community we believed that those people who does not go to Mosque or pray to Allah; it is like a punishment according to our Qur'an. You are also Muslim Datu right? (laughing). It is because Allah commands us to pray on him to avoid any sickness, this includes mental illness of a person. It's like, you have weak foundation or faith...

Other mythical beliefs in the community was that they believed in possession of what they called "Deping" and "Jinns". Deping is a term unique to the community especially those who is practicing healing in barrios. Usually they are the last resort for healing. Deping according to Babo Pakong is what they considered the twin of an individual who is ill and only the ill person and the faith healer, Taligamot, could see it. According to Babo Pakong, not everyone has a twin. This twin possessed the material body to express his or her own concern or needs particularly to the person having it. This includes the need to have shelter, food, and water. The ritual is done by providing food prepared by Taligamot or faith healer together with a ritual such as Sagayan and Kulintang to release that spirit of the twin. This practice of Maguindanaon culture was peculiar, in fact, literature on this practice is limited. Aside from this Deping, the general concept of possession is the possession of Jinns which is part of the belief of Islam. This Jinns is another race but unlike Deping, Jinns possessed Muslims who disobeyed Allah because of weak foundation spiritually. The possession of Jinns and Deping if not treated immediately leads to mental illness according to the participants.

Below are the responses of Babo Pakung, Babo Kuri, and Bapa Abdul:

...Na makadpsabap bun enan, sa kabuneg mika di nengka kapapagamutan salkita taligamot. Ka aden bun san ni kay, nyanon bai mga suld nen sa naukitan nengka, na maga ustds ged a benal sila. na bale meto ba, maya mga kaasalan, dala naneguma lun na maya katawi kaden eh mga ustds ah kwana2x sila nen ? ngen nani di silan mamalityala sa aden kaasalan, na maya kwana bu enan. shaitan bun enan. maya pedshaitanan bu enan . na na tuba na dla nilan papagamuti na tuba e pakakagkaed lun na maya pedsasagayanan, pendepingan... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

...One cause of his mental illness was he were not immediately treated and referred to Taligamot. We have one case of daughter by Ustds wherein we believed that it is caused by "not like ours", her Deping. However, Muslim leaders do not believe on it. They said it's just Shaitan who possessed his daughter. Then they didn't bring the child to taligamot (Faith healer). We suggested them to bring it to a faith healer to perform a ritual and Depingan...

...Na enani masu kwana. E kena kapanan. Ehh na nanbumba. Nani ah pa, egkwana na deping nen. Taw dekana mga nee, nge kana

kanga kawana, pesaytanan, pedsaytanan, na tuoba... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...AHmm what, there is that what we called “di kapanan” or “not like ours”, and that possessed by his or her “Deping” (referring to a person’s twin which cannot be seen by normal people - Maguindanao’s culture), people possessed by shaitan or evil. That’s it...

...nah sakabyas bun man e nyabay ngen..aden bun manem eehhh ehh egkayaw ah eh matenggaw nan a ehh aden ato nan aa magaga na sya bun sa lekitaw nya nen mana naumba ah mga deping deping bun, mga kaasalan, metun ba.....nah katawan nenka? na pagasukan na deping, na sya sa lekita, na pagpagumon, papegkanen, ando pangeni sekanin sa pegken nen... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...They are actually really different, like this. they will feel so hot, and then feeling cold. in this case, we can treat this kind of sickness. because it is caused by Deping (persons’ twin) they are unique on us...did you know the reason, possession of our twin in our community should be treated in a way that we should give their own shares, because we believed that you and your twin should have the same shares of foods clothing and others...

...aahnn kagutem. ahnn metu ba. pagpagumon bas a balgkas. pangeni sa balgkas ando makan nen... di, si parekoy ah na deping nen bun enan uway a masukwana na nakatulan den enan.m akabuneg bun makaanteng-ateng bun enan mekaw dili den manggalbek .makatulan ah di ren magaga. din magaga... di masambet na nanba semimabuneg ba sekanin ahh... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...yes, the get hungry also, not just in foods but also in clothing, you have to share everything of you or else they will be possessed you... no, Parengkoy is also having deping, but in our belief, his case was left untreated causing it to develop into mental illness. yes, it can cause mental illness, if left untreated at early stage, there’s no cure already...

if not treated immediately, it can lead into insanity...

...mikaw mamba kay dutin na (pakingkoy) ka mikaw magamutan na egkapyo bun. ugayd na imposible den samana lekanin ah ka nauget den. Kapangagyan ento... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q3)

...no, parekoy is also having deping, but in our belief, his case was left untreated causing it to develop into mental illness. Yes, it can cause mental illness, if left untreated at early stage, there’s no cure already...

...di ka nyaka tuba ka kwana nengka tuba NYA edatulan a tumba ka kabuneg. na ma eh mikaw tu ba e egkandalu nen na maami ko un anto na edtalu ne. aden anto ah edtlu nen eh katawan ko maya enya a deping nen panguntol sa kakan nin. na na edtalan buh sa maya o nan bun ba eh kapegkakarta kapegkandalo nengka sa nan na pagumanan eh deping nen kandu paegkanen, na pagkapyo kanen den. ka pakanen. enggan sa balgkas nen. na egkapa den ban to. uway ah penguin ta bun ento... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q1)

...No, if it is really a person who are possessed, he or she will tell me her identity whenever i hold his or her hand, you will know it’s his or her deping and he or she will find some foods to eat, and also clothes. then after that, I will command her/him to cast out from the person’s body then that person will be getting back to consciousness...

Bapa Abdul’s statement on his belief on mental illness as caused by possession of Jinns below:

...Ahn samin din naniniwala kami sa tinatawag na JINNS, eto sila yung mga parang shaitan na sumasanib sa taong di nagsasambayang. Pagasukan a nya ban a pegkabagel ged sekanila, and bpaygo sila sa ig...(Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

...We also believe in what we called Jinns, they are like shaitan, but they are mortal also, they cannot be seen individuals. This will be possessed those who do not pray to God. Possessed people tends to be very strong, and wants to submerge in the water...

Another myth on the cause of mental illness is excessive headache due to the exposure to the sun. According to Babo Pakong, too much exposure to the sun and Pasmu (not able to eat on time) can lead severe headache which may have caused the person to have mental illness. Also, too much loneliness caused headache which eventually could develop to mental illness as they believe. Babo Pakong stated that:

...nge nani pegkakasakit eh ulo nin... aden mambu nge nani pekakasakit eh ulo nila nen? Nya na kasublan na kadtingangang.....ngan pan, pekakasakit ba eh ulo nen.. panald, di pakakan sa mapya. malate sa kakan..na sya pebpawang sa ulo. naegkakasakit den so ulo. egkakasakit eh utek nin. andu malidu eh ginawa nin nan a egkasakit bun e ulo nin. sabap sa lu ba eh kalidu nu ginawa anto na lu ba pebpawang sa ulo ah. Kalidu na ginawa nen... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q1)

...excessive headache...excessive headache due to exposure to the sun...it can cause...what else, she will run after you, “Pasmu”, then excessive headache, these can cause mental illness...and too much loneliness, this loneliness can cause headache and then makes him insane...

The above themes are extracted from the different experiences of Maguindanao community on people having mental illness in their mainstream in which they experienced struggles with these individuals. Despite this challenging experience, cases such as discrimination is not evident during the interview, instead, the researcher observed the sympathy of the participants to these people with mental illness. Some of the participants’ view on mental illness is conventional which originated from the culture itself. However, there are still who believed that people with mental illness can be treated using a modern practice such as treatment in facilities with

the help of mental health professionals. Table 2 below shows the results based on the thematic analysis of all statements.

Table 2. Major Themes and Core Ideas on Relevant Experiences of Maguindanaon Community Regarding People with Mental Illness

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Risk of aggression and violence	Throwing stones anywhere; people had to hide/avoid Punches people; throws anything he gets his hands into Threatened to kill; cut people; capable of hurting people Won't hesitate to hurt people when mistreated Is very aggressive, shows bizarre behavior; runs after people Threatened because they do things without provocations Became aggressive; becomes violent with family/parents Gets angry very easily; becomes out of control Restless, keeps punching in the air, talking to self Acts weird, does weird things
Unusual and off the wall actuations	Whispers to self, talks excessively, and incessantly Keeps picking trashes Doesn't sleep at night; keeps walking around; restless and anxious Laughs alone; keeps on running around and laughing about Walks in the middle of the night, accuses parents of hiding husband Defecates in the room, so had to be kept and tied Distressed, no proper hygiene, unkempt hair, smelly Cannot understand flow of conversation; always out of topic; Are mournful, lonely, malnourished
Wretchedness and object despondency	Asking for food; attempting to suicide Troubled sleep, overthinking Separated from husband, blames parents Was a drug user/dependent; became wasted because of drugs Got influenced by friends to use shabu Seems to be beyond treatment With suicidal tendencies; hanged self with a rope Became insane because of drug overuse Develop mental illness even without the use of drugs
Facts and myths on mental illness	Too much exposure to the sun "Deping" can lead to mental illness if not treated early Became mentally ill because not given immediately treatment It is a punishment by God; It is caused by "Deping" People acquire mental illness because of traumatic experience Brought about by genetic predisposition

Maguindanaon community coping with the challenges on people having mental illness

Five (5) Themes were extracted from the participants' responses on the question "What are the coping mechanism of Maguindanaon Community on the challenges they faced with individual having mental illness in the mainstream?". These are the following: Strong faith in Allah; Giving and seeking intervention and support; Generosity of spirits; Kindness and acceptance; and Avoidance. Themes are derived from the core ideas presented in table three (3) below.

Strong faith in Allah. Strong faith in Allah as coping mechanism was seen to be one of the themes on how the community deals among this individual. In everything that happens among the community, they tend to submit themselves to Allah. Prayer or Sallah and reading Qur'an are what they find effective in coping with their problems, this is considered the foundation of faith. Lack of this activity may lead everyone into developing such illness according to the participants. This illness in addition, is believed to be the will of Allah who is the creator. Bapa Tahir insisted that everyone should strengthen their own faith to Allah in order to conquer any problem the individual is facing. As an Imam in the community, Bapa Rasul any problem such as mental illness can be cured by reading Qur'an which according to him the answers of all question by humanity. Below are statements of Bapa Tahir, Bapa Abdul and Bapa Rasul:

...sa spiritual na aspeto naman, kasi ang pinakafoundation dun yung ah strong foundation natin sa paniniala sa dioys na walang illness na hindi pwedeng magamot sa tulong o intervention ng ating panginoon. So ang pinaka basic doon siguro na kanilang pananao is pagpapatibay ng ating spiritual na paniwala. Na kahit anong mangyare, bastat strong ang foundation ng spiritual foundation natin, ah maconquer natin kung ano man mga problema na maging cause ng ganitong illness... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q2)

...In spiritual aspect, the very foundation on that is the foundation or belief in God, that no illnesses can be cured without the help or

intervention of God. So, the basic there I think is the perception is strengthening our spiritual belief. That whatever your situations are, for as long as you have a strong foundation, of spiritual foundation, then we can conquer all these problems that can cause this illness...

...ang pinaka- importante, magsimba araw2x para maiwasan yung sakit sa utak. Kung nagkaroon ka naman nito, pwde kang magpaconsulta sa doctor na specialized sa sakit sa utek... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q2)

...The most important one, we need to pray every day for avoid mental illness. If you already have it, then consult to a doctor specialized in mental illness...

...Maya inya po, in fact, sa Islam ay may kasabihan si abu allah maududi, “naka saad sa qur’an lahat ng tanong ng tao, masasagot sa qur’an na ito...eto rin ang sagot andu makagamot para mawala ang mga sakit kasama na ang sakit ng isang tao sa utak” ... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q2)

...It’s like this, in fact, Islam has saying in Qur’an, all questions of humanity, they can be answered in Qur’an, this is also the answer to heal or cure all diseases including mental illness...

Giving and seeking intervention and support. Another theme derived from the narratives of the participants created another coping mechanism. Wherein the participants help these individuals by supporting them financially, emotionally and even physically. Also, seeking intervention such as bringing them to professionals and paraprofessional to treat the condition of these individuals and lastly, the role of family is also another coping to this individual. Babo Pakong said that they had several options, that is depending on the case of an individual. She advised that individual should seek Taligamot or faith healer first, followed by a medical doctor if there is no evidence of improvement. If this case cannot be treated by a medical doctor, then the community seek intervention from Imam or Ustadz who is a Muslim religious leader. She gave an example of a case of another neighborhood who after several years of working abroad, developed mental illness. After she was sent back from overseas, the family decided to bring her to faith healers or Taligamot but her condition seemed to have gotten worse. This led the family to seek medical help from professionals, they were surprised that her ability to recover was fast. Bapa Rasul also agreed that they give support to these individuals by bringing them to near institution where proper intervention and medication is being utilized. In addition, most participants agreed that social support is very important for these individuals to recover from their illness; that giving and seeking intervention to support people having mental illness is part of the coping mechanism of these individuals. As what Babo Pakong, Bapa Rasul, Bapa Daud, Bapa Abdul and Babo Kuri said:

...na upama ka eh nyata edsipatan na so dalu nen ka upama lu dayt sa doctor na na doctor. na upama ka eh sya kwana ka sya sa lekita, na sya man sa lekita nu paagamutan... penggamutan dan den sa lekita, oh dala bun, di bun ekapya nae lo ta sa doctor. .aden anto nana upaman ka Makalu ta sa doctor ka di bun pegkapy na isya ta manem sa lekita. Ustads den maenm... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...for example, we need to observe if this person needs doctor, if they are appropriate to be treated by doctors. But if need to be treated in our own ways as Muslim, then look for Taligamot...First, refer them to Taligamot, if there seems no improvement, then bring them to doctor, then if there is no improvement again, then last resort is our USTADS, or religious leader...

...engkay aden lu pakiwatan ni laida. Bale nakauli magabroad, mana kabuneg ba tamug a endaguy magulyan andu edtatawa. Na penadsipatan na masukwana ginamutan sya sa lekita . guna soo naebped den gamut sa lekitano, na dala bun, nan a inet nila lu sa isulan, mental...na migkapyo tengka. megkapyo bun... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...Look at the niece of Laida, after she came back from abroad, she seems becoming mentally ill, she runs at times, crying, and laughing without any reason. She was treated in taligamot first but seems no improvement, she was admitted to mental hospital in Isulan.. now she is already fine... it’s really a doctor...

...uway mayroon na madekel den mambo, yung iba ahh yung nakulong na yung iba..narehab yun sa dun sa amas, gensan, pero hndi naman lahat ng nakulong ay gumagamit... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q2)

...Yes, we have a lot actually, some are now at jail, already detained, some are in rehab like in Gensan and Amas, but not all detained are drug users...

...insights?ahmmm siguro more on, this people needs extra care by their relatives, it is because one of the factor for these people from not being able to recover is the lack of care and love by relatives, most especially the immediate family. Another one, we should not treat this people as someone who is defective but instead, we should not judgement, we should feel them that they are still accepted by the community... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q2)

...Insights? ahmmm I think more on, this people needs extra care by their relatives, it is because one of the factor for these people from not being able to recover is the lack of care and love by relatives, most especially the immediate family. Another one, we should not treat this people as someone who is defective but instead, we should not judgement, we should feel them that they are still accepted by the community...

... siguro nananakot siya dahil nakikita nya maraming umiiwas sa kanila....siguro pag alagaan natin sila kay magiging okay rin sila gaya natin... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q2)

... I think they scary us because they observed that many are avoiding them. I think if we take good care of them, the soon they will be fine like us...

...depende sa case, pag ganyan na pinag uusapan kay nagtaty din kami minsan sa mga parang albularyo kung sanib2x yan...pag mental illness kay sa doctor dapat..pero wala kasing doctor dto talaga na residence sa amin lugar...mga midwife lang...(Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q2)

...It depends upon the case, if it is Deping, we approach an albularyo or mangagamot if it is more on possession. And if it is mental illness, we seek an advice from medical doctor. But in this community, we have no doctor, we only have midwife...

...pwede siguro sa religious na aspeto, yung ating mga ustads, yung mayroon mga malawak na kaalaman na related naman sa spiritual. siguro malaking tulong ito para tayo ay mabigyan ng tamang direction. maliban sa mga ustads, mayroon din mga manggagmaot ng nag-uundergo ng rituals na pwde nilang isagawa para at least makita kung ito ba ay makakatulong dun sa tao na may mentalillness... (Bapa Tahir)

...in the religious aspect, might be they are the ustads, who have wide knowledge related to spiritual. i think they are big help to give them direction. aside from ustads, we have also faith healer who undergo some rituals which can be done to see if it is helpful to that person having mental illness...

Unfortunately, there are some individuals with mental illness who are late admitted to a Taligamot (faith healer) and remain untreated due to resistance of the family who are not believers of the faith healer's intervention according to Babo Pakong. The families of these people believed that their condition was caused by Satan or Jinn possession and not Deping possession. Babo Pakong said:

...Na makadpsabap bun enan, sa kabuneg mika di nengka kapapagamutan salkita taligamot. Ka aden bun san ni kay, nyanon bai mga suld nen sa naukitan nengka, na maga ustads ged a benal sila. na bale meto ba, maya mga kaasalan, dala naneguma lun na maya katawi kaden eh mga ustads ah kwana2x sila nen ? ngen nani di silan mamalityala sa aden kaasalan, na maya kwana bu enan. shaitan bun enan. maya pedshaitanan bu enan . na na tuba na dla nilan papagamuti na tuba e pakakagkaed lun na maya pedsasagayanan, pendepingan. niya nila edtalun, ...enduken ka nya pakakwana netun a mga shaitan bu inan.. na da nylan papagamuti . taman sa tubun ba e kinabuneg nen. nana pekwanan..aden walay nilan san ni na mambeg na luh nilan ba pelugenen.di nilan a benal palyon.eehn ka tupan ka limyo na biyas2x eh pedpalasen nen tingka nanbai sld ni dido ah si pia e ngala nin... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

...One cause of his mental illness was he were not immediately treated and referred to taligamot. We have one case of daughter by Ustads wherein we believed that it is caused by "not like ours", her Deping. However, Muslim leaders do not believe on it. They said it's just Shaitan who possessed his daughter. Then they didn't bring the child to taligamot (Fatih healer). We suggested them to bring it to a faith healer to perform a ritual and Depingan. Eventually she develops mental illness. They keep her in one room to prevent her from hurting others. She became violent that time. Her name was PIA...

Generosity of spirits. Generosity is evident as how they cope with this individual. The community shows their generosity by giving this individual support, financially and emotionally. Most participants show their support for these individuals by providing them foods, not treating them as different and even providing them shelter in the community despite of their less fortunate situation. Babo Pakong said that if there are events or celebrations, they invited Dutin and others. Through this, they might feel that they still belong to the community.

This is also true to Bapa Rasul who said that whenever these individuals are asking for foods to eat, they tend to them although when they are at risk of aggression at times, they just avoided them until they become much calmer again. Babo Kuri who stand as second mother of Dutin in fact helped this person to build his own house near them. To Babo Kuri, they can monitor Dutin from time to time. Babo Kuri also added that he is still helpful to them like sharing household chores, Dutin is asked to cut firewoods, fetch water and some other requests as long as there is given reward such as cigarettes and food to eat. Below are the statements of Babo Pakong, Bapa Rasul and Babo Kuri:

...na nya nen bu makatabang a mekaw aden makan ah (hahahahahahah) andu sugon. di.. nya nen makadtabang sa lekita nu na mekaw sugon, ma malityala mambu..malityala bun sekanin. asel kaenggan sa makan nen... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q2)

...What he can do, if there are food to eat, he can eat also be invited... (laughing).in joke part.... No, he despite of his condition is also helpful in our community. If you are going to ask him something in favor, he will follow it given that there should be any reward after, like foods to eat...

...copinggg...Nyako penggula na lemikay mambo, ka minsan pakagelk sekanilan..Ngan pan? Ahhm aden anto mekaw pakasya bas a maubay salka, na pagengan sa peken nen...tub a...(Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q2)

...Coping...what I usually did is to avoid this people, because at times they are violent. What else?...ahhmmm at times when they usually ask for food in this house, then we give them foods to eat...nothing else...

...na o meka maya ehh kwaka pan eh tuy DOTS ka pakanen ka buh, nana kun nen bun mambu e tuba ehhn, ugayd na mikaw ebpyan- pyanan nengka mambo sekannin, na malityala bun sekanin tuba apya dala den. ... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

... For example, can you please help us on this, on that? Then we'll give you some foods to eat. That's it. And also, even without any reward, for as long as you requested him in a well-mannered, then he will eventually say yes...

... ehhn...sekanin den mun ah menumbal lun..ugayd na penangenggan den mun sa mga kay una nakambalay...na matag den mambu man a tangka datu omar ah matilak ged samana, malimpy a benal eh kapendetal nen, kapegkagamitan nen..uway na utek nen ma. di mun kasabutan utek nen man ba anan eh maskwana. (c: aden deperensya nen)...eehhnn...enya anda den man anto san... da bun guna luh kila didu ah?... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

... Yes, he is actually the one who build it, but we give him some money to buy materials. Despite of his situation in fact, he is really neat and organized person on his own house. However, mentally defective. We cannot understand his mentality...

...mikaw dala den ba kakan nin ka na pagenggan den manem sekanin. Ehhn para dili..para pakakan manem sekanin. no dala manem na aden kapangenyan nen na aden paggenggan sekanin... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q1)

...if he does not have any foods to eat, then we give him some foods. For as long as we have our own, then, we give him...

Kindness and acceptance. This theme emerged from the idea that Maguindanaon community expresses their concern among this individual by being kind and supportive to this people and accepting them as part of the community. Most participants suggested that individual with mental illness in the mainstream needs wide understanding. Bapa Tahir agreed that we as normal people should be the one to understand this individual which supported by Bapa Abdul and Babo Kuri who said people in the community should exert an effort to take care of them because the condition they have is not really their choice. Below are the statements of Bapa Tahir, Babo Kuri, and Bapa Abdul:

...ahh ang pwde kong masabi sa ganitong situation ay tayo bilang normal na tayo yung unang may pang unawa sa mga ganito kas inga wala sila sa tamang katinuan, may mga actuations na kung normal lamang guro sila na tao ay andun parin yung hiya bilang tao na may dignidad. Kasi yung yung mga actuations na siala lang yung gumagawa dahil nga wala sila sa tamang katinuan. So tayo yung unang dapat na umuunawa sa gnitong situation... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

...ahh what I can say in this situation is that, we as a normal people, we should be the one to understand this people. There are some actuations wherein if they are just a normal people, shame is still there as a person with dignity. Because they are doing such actuations because they are in that kind of mentality. So, we should be the one who should understand them.

...ahm insights.yung nga...dapat alagaan natin sila kahit hindi pa natin sila kaano-2x ang importante dapat di natin ipakita sa mga tao na anden sakit nen sa utak.. na sakabias sila..kasi yung ang possible nag pwdeng makatrigger sa knila,,mikaw iwasan nengka or pinagtatawanan natin sila..so ahmm instead dapat ipakita parin natin yung magandang asal sa knila dahil di naman nila kasalan maging ganoon sila perhaps no?... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

...Ahmm insights ...that's it, we need to take good care of them even though they are not our family, the important thing is we should not treat them as if they are different from us. Because this might trigger them. If you will avoid them or laugh at them. Instead, we need to show to them the good attitude to them because it is not their fault to have it...

...Dala ka pedpyan-pyanan nami bun ..di nami papamakairanan...di nami pamedtwan sa maya buneg..ka pedpyan-pyanan nami sekanin, na mikaw da kakan nin, na pagneggan nami sekanin sa makan. kayna katawan nami mambu sekanin ah marupang-dupang.ehhn. di ta paka-eng sa maya sa lekita na mapya eh kapagutek nen ka kagina katawan ta sekanin na limban bun den eh utek nen... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

...We're just taking care of him; we never make him feel that he is different. We do not laugh at him and say he has mental illness. If he is nothing to eat, then we give him some foods to eat, because we know his condition that he has mental illness. We cannot compare him to us with normal people and we know in the first place that he is already detached...

Avoidance. Most participants avoid and hide from these individuals because of perceived threat especially when these individuals relapse. Bapa Abdul narrated his experience when he was young, when Babo "Grace" who suffers from mental illness ran after him after she caught him climbing trees in her yard. This made Bapa Abdul develop fear of people with mental illness. This is true among other participants. They tried to avoid people having mental illness in the community because of fear that they might hurt anyone, get wild and become uncontrollable. This led people in the community to avoid these people when they relapse as much as possible. Bapa Abdul, Bapa Daud, Bapa Rasul and Babo Lanie said:

... iwas talaga,since pakagelik ged baka may dala dala pa syang kutsilyo ba...marami nga umiiwas sa kanya....ang ginagawa ko iniiwasan ko nalang dumaan doon sa malapit bahay nila pag ako lang mag isa.....(Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q2)

...Really. To avoid, since she is threatening for me, might be she is bringing knife or anything. There are a lot who also avoiding her. What I did at times I just avoiding passing by to their house when I am alone walking...

...Ahmm, umiiwas ako minsan depede sa kaharap ko, baka sila yung nanakit so iwas, and always I have indifferent reactions since they are not my business. Tinapakitaan ko lang na parang normal lang sila... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q2)

...Ahhmm, avoiding sometimes it depends on the encountered one, might be they are hurtful so, I avoid, and always I have indifferent reactions since they are not my business. I just showed to them that they are like the normal one....

Mikaw kandauma namba a kapegkabunegen buba anan a pedtaka kami pamagena ka eh pamengel sa mga walay... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q2)

...Every time she gets triggered, we are scared and avoid since she keeps on throwing things anywhere...

...Nyako penggula na lemikay mambo, ka minsan pakagelk sekanilan..ngen pan? Ahhm aden anto mekaw pakasya bas a maubay salka, na pagangan sa peken nen...tub a... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q2)

...what I usually did is to avoid this people, because at times they are violent. What else? ahmmmm at times when they usually ask for food in this house, then we give them foods to eat...nothing else...

Table 3. Major Themes and Core Ideas on how Maguindanaon community cope with the challenges on people having mental illness

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Strong faith in Allah	Having a strong foundation of faith
	Will of Allah that they become what they have become
	Pray to Allah for deliverance from mental illness
Giving and seeking intervention and support	All questions of humanity can be answered in Qur'an
	They must be reinforced spiritually
	Bringing them to "Taligamot" or to Ustadz
	Finding some kind of intervention
	Find an institution that can help them
	Care of relatives/family is important
	Support from significant persons in their life
Generosity of spirits	Undergo some rituals to drive the illness away
	Just taking care of them
	Giving food to eat when they are hungry; providing shelter
	Just sharing some blessings i.e. food
	Giving them something to eat when they ask
	Showing kindness and mercy
	Understand why they are like that
Kindness and acceptance	Accept them as they are; not make them feels different
	Not considering them as outcasts of society
	Making them feel that they belong; that they are accepted
	Treating them the same; not as different people
	Trying not to agitate them any further
	Letting them be when they get wild and throws a fit
Avoidance	Should not laugh/joke when they are around
	Not giving up on them; understanding them
	Just avoiding them for safety purposes
	Stay away from them as they have the tendency to be violent
	No judgements, but avoid them for safety
	They have to be put somewhere they can't harm people

Maguindanaon Community Insights They Can Share Regarding the Experiences with People Having Mental Illness

After a careful examining of the participant's responses, several themes were drawn from the insights of Muslim community regarding their experiences on people having mental illness in the mainstream. These themes are the following: Lack of strong spiritual foundation and faith in Allah; Major stress and trauma in life; Lack of appropriate treatment and medication; and Lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support.

Lack of strong spiritual foundation and faith in Allah. This theme was drawn from the insight of the community wherein lack of foundation to Allah was seen as a reason on why people develop mental illness and to be able to reconcile these individuals means to strengthen the faith to Allah. Lack of this spiritual foundation according to Bapa Rasul and Bapa Abdul was characterized by not going to Mosque to pray, disobedience to Allah, and by not reading Qur'an. Thus, leading the individual to problematic situations, mental illnesses, and possession of Jinns or Shaitan which served as a form of Allah's punishment. To avoid any illness, majority of the participants agreed that every individual should strengthen their faith to Allah by praying five (5) times a day, visit a Mosque, and read the Muslim bible. These daily activities prevent the individuals from any kinds of illnesses. Below are the statements of the participants Bapa Rasul, Bapa Abdul, and Bapa Tahir whom during the interview, they really asserted this lack of foundation and faith to Allah:

...positive experience manem, relaization?, ahhh matag mambu pakagelk samaya enya ba mga tao, na mapagitong ku mun eh aden reason nengan ka nakagkumaya sekanin...basi madakel din mawn eh prolema nen...si Allah eh mataw sa knilan, basi kahanda bun no kadenan enyala...we should not judge this these people... mana sya sa laki, I think, another cause is when you try to be disobeyed Allah...its actually will of god to punish you for not visiting Mosque to pray... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q3)

...Positive experience, realization? even though they have this condition, even though at times we are afraid of them, I realized that I think there are reasons why this people became like this, maybe they have a lot of problem. And Allah will just take care of them, I think it's the will of Allah why they become like that. we should not judge this these people...In my own views, I think, another cause is when you try to be disobeyed Allah...its actually will of god to punish you for not visiting Mosque to pray...

...tpos samin naniniwala kasi kami na pag hindi ka ng mosque or sumamba kay Allah (SWA), parang punishment yan samin...satin pala according to Qur'an, muslim ka rin pala datu hahah... (laughing). Dahil ang sugo ni allah, kailangan syang sambahin para walang sakit na tumalab sayo, kasama na diyang ang sakit sa utak ng tao ...kumbaga weak ang faith and foundation mo... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

... then in our community we believed that those people who does not go to Mosque or pray to Allah; it is like a punishment according to our Qur'an. You are also Muslim Datu right? (laughing). It is because Allah commands us to pray on him to avoid any sickness, this includes mental illness of a person. It's like, you have weak foundation or faith...

... sa pananampalataya, pananalig natin sa diyos, pagsamba, paglapit satin panginoon in case n merun tayong mga ganoon. Kasi isa sa strong foundation natin duon ay YUNG sa FAITH natin pananalig kung paano natin haharapin ang ganitong situation... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... In religious aspect, it's the faith to God, praying to God in terms of having that. Because our strong foundation is our faith on how we face the situation...

... sa spiritual na aspeto naman, kasi ang pinakafoundation dun yung ah strong foundation natin sa paniniala sa dioys na walang illness na hindi pwedeng magamot sa tulong o intervention ng ating panginoon. So ang pinaka basic doon siguro na kanilang pananao is pagpapatibay ng ating spiritual na paniiwala. Na kahit anong mangyare, bastat strong ang foundation ng spiritual foundation natin, ah maconquer natin kung ano man mga problema na maging cause ng ganitong illness... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... In spiritual aspect, the very foundation on that is the foundation or belief in God, that no illnesses can be cured without the help or intervention of God. So, the basic there I think is the perception is strengthening our spiritual belief. That whatever your situations are, for as long as you have a strong foundation, of spiritual foundation, then we can conquer all these problems that can cause this illness...

... Ahn samin din naniniwala kami sa tinatawag na JINNS, eto sila yung mga parang shaitan na sumasanib sa taong di nagsasambayang. Pagasukan a nya ban a pegkabagel ged sekanila, and bpaygo sila sa ig... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

... We also believe in what we called Jinns, they are like shaitan, but they are mortal also, they cannot be seen individuals. This will be possessed those who do not pray to God. Possessed people tends to be very strong, and wants to submerge in the water...

Major stress and trauma in life. This theme was drawn from the insights of most participants where according to them, genetic factors and aversive environment of these individuals play a role in developing mental illness. Bapa Daud, Bapa Tahir and Babo Lanie stated that individuals develop mental illness because of inherited predisposition towards the illness triggered by the aversive environment where the individual is situated. Below are the statements of Bapa Daud, Bapa Tahir and Babo Lanie:

... aden andto ka nait then sa kapenggemaw nin. Nanba eh malgen den ah kait sa kapenggmaw nin... (Babo Lanie) (m4a_P3_Q1)

... For some, they are inherited form birth. In that case, it is impossible to treat this people...

... Yang nga no, stressful environment, not so supportive people around us, biological cause and also can be like genetic factors...dala na kumbaga muli lang ginising ng experience at environment niya ang illness. Para siyang cancer, people who are having family history of cancer are more likely to develop it depending on his lifestyle... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

... That's it, stressful environment, not so supportive people around us, biological cause and also can be like genetic factors...already there and triggered by the experiences and environment. It' like a cancer, people who are having family history of cancer are more likely to develop it depending on his lifestyle...

... Sa na- observation ko as my perception, ito mga mental illness ay nag uugat ito sa mas malalim siguro na problema ah or maari naman itong siguro kung scientific naman, nakikita natin na nasa hereditary, or my history sa family pero kung iset aside natin ang yung sa hereditary, siguro nag uugat to sa mas malalim na trauma sa buhay or experiences nila na kanilang naencounter sa kanilang komunidad or sa pamilya mismo. ahh ... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... Based on my observation, and as for my perception, mental illness stems from an intensive problem, or might be if it is scientific one, we can see that it is hereditary, or having the history in the family. However, if we set aside the heredity, I think it stems from an intensive trauma in life or experiences that they encounter in their community or in the family...

Babo Pakong believed that negative experiences can lead the person to experience drastic changes which eventually might turn to mental illness. The case of Babo Pia (a person having mental illness) illustrates this condition where the community believed that she developed her condition due to the problem with her estranged husband. She was not able to handle the situation well, she went through heavy stress that led to her mental illness. In fact, she's had delusions that her husband was kept and hidden by her own parents. Babo Kuri, Bapa Abdul and Bapa Daud supported this notion of Babo Pakong on stress and trauma. Below are the statements of Babo Pakong and Babo Kuri, Bapa Abdul and Bapa Daud:

... den a mekaw kasublan na etong nen ba na na tub a mabuneg ba ka eeh ka bae to bay ah si BABO Pia ba ah di ged pakatulog, panalday... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q3)

... If that person is overthinking, it can lead to insanity, sleep disturbances while most of the time holding hairbrush. Babo Pia is a good example...

... si babo nani di ged makatug ka pedsendetan nen sekanin eh napambelag sa lekanilan na si ama nen andu si ina nen. pembetay nen e tuba si ama nen ah ahh nakametal tangka... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q1)

... Babo, who is also our neighborhood. her parents cannot sleep well because she keeps on blaming her parents for their separation with her husband. She keeps on spanking her parents. In fact, she was admitted to mental hospital...

... aden anto na kasublan sa problema nan, di nen den kakaya eh problema nen, na kakwana den sekanin., kaanteng-anteng sekanin. kabuneg den sekanin... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q3)

... At times, because of excessive problems, and she cannot handle it. Then she will eventually be triggered...

... For me, one reason was, pag mikaw nasuran na problema, subrang stress and down na sya masyadong sa daming problema nanba eh pakadsakit sa utek naa tao... (Bapa Abdul) (m4a_P8_Q3)

... For me, one reason was when we are bombarded with many problems, too much stress, down because of many problems these are reasons for mental illness...

... Hmm... mental illness if brought about by stress from the environment specially people nowadays are competing to each other resulting into less love and caring...therefore mental illness is not just brought about by physical or biological alterations of the brain but also it involves person's lifestyle...and the culture around him, at least in my profession... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

... Hmm... mental illness if brought about by stress from the environment specially people nowadays are competing to each other resulting into less love and caring...therefore mental illness is not just brought about by physical or biological alterations of the brain but also it involves person's lifestyle...and the culture around him, at least in my profession...

In general, the statements of the participants above have shown the vital role of one's genetic origin and environmental stressors as contributing factors in the development of mental illness in individuals.

Lack of appropriate treatment and mental health professionals. Lack of appropriate treatment or right medication and lack of mental health professionals was seen as a major problem in terms of helping people to recover from mental illness in the community. Most participants agreed on the idea of rehabilitation as an appropriate action to take for people who are engaged in drug addiction resulting to the illness, they should take any modern scientific treatment like medication right away.

However, the community has no mental health professionals such as psychiatrist and psychologist resulting to lack of enough knowledge on the right treatments and medications, this situation leads the community to seek Taligamot or faith healer. In addition, according to Bapa Tahir of University of Southern Mindanao, there are some seminars on mental health, but they do not talk about mental health treatment and intervention, instead they focus solely on awareness in terms of how prevalent it is. Lastly, majority of the participants such as Babo Dido, Bapa Tahir, and Bapa Daud agreed that treatment and medication as intervention should be administered by certified mental health professionals to properly treat individuals suffering from mental illness. Statements of the participants are below:

... And if it is mental illness, we seek an advice from medical doctor. But in this community, we have no doctor, we only have midwife... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... And if it is mental illness, we seek an advice from medical doctor. But in this community, we have no doctor, we only have midwife...

... eeehhhh angan-angan nen ka haha (laughing) malgen den man enan guna magaga guna si parengkoy ah. Ka ehh kwana den enan.ehh ngen paniee..sya sa doctor sa mental den enan... (Babo Pakong) (m4a_P5_Q3)

...ahmm...seems to be impossible (hahaha) it would be difficult already to treat Parengkoy. It is because, what do we call that? It's more appropriate on doctor in mental...

.... parang more on awareness lang ahmm kulang pa yung siguro pamamaraan kung paano natin mabibigyan ng emphasis na tayo mismo sa level natin bilang hindi medical practitioner ay magkakaroon na kahit man lang maliit na pamamaraan paano natin

mabigyan ng emphasis ang pag intindi and pag identify kung merun tayong mgaexperiences na ganito sa loob ng school... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... It's only like more on awareness, this methods or ways are not sufficient on how to emphasize in our level who is not a medical practitioner. We need to have for even in a little way, we can understand and identify if there's such experience inside the school...

... anden gamut nen? na nanba e dayt a ah mikaw maytuba sa upama ah eh drugs ba anto eh nakabuneg lun. Na tumba e neggay lun a gamot a gamot ah mga drugs bun ba anto. maawa eh effect ah drugs anto. kagina nanba sekanin ah maya edtawn nila maya pila lagun buh eh effect a druag santo ah maawa bun. Ugayd anan na nauget den a dala bun kaawa... (Babo Kuri) (m4a_P2_Q3)

... If there is medication, then that is the appropriate one. For example, if it is brought about by illegal drugs, then medication appropriate for that is necessary. That is to counteract the effects...

Lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support. Another theme drawn from participants' insight was the problem on treatment facilities and proper support programs for individuals having mental illness. Some of the emerging issues include medication cost which is too expensive which cannot be sustained by the families, lack of institution or treatment facilities, and even professionals to treat these individuals. Lastly, support from significant people and the government were seen as another issue which contributes to the inappropriate treatment of mental illness.

According to Bapa Daud, he insisted that the local government should take action to address the issue on mental health. That is, to establish an institution and provide a low-cost medical treatment to improve the condition among individuals suffering from mental illness. This was agreed by Bapa Tahir and Bapa Rasul. In fact, according to Bapa Tahir, they have limited medical doctor so instead of seeking them for professional help, the community tend to approach a midwife as their medical adviser. Bapa Rasul stated that they needed to bring a person with mental illness to neighboring town or city such as General Santos City and Amas to rehabilitate a person with mental illness. The following are the statements of the participants:

... nyako madtalo na sa lekita no eh mga tao na anden sakit nin sa utek, ugayd, wala pa masyadong facilities na known specially sa atin community na mag aalaga sa mga taong may kapansanan sa utak...(Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

... What I can say is that there are a lot of us people in the community having mental illness, but there are not enough facilities that is known especially in our community which will take care with these people having mental illnesses...

... ahhh..Yung nga, mental illness is becoming more rampant, I mean a lot of people nowadays are suffering from this illness...so we should establish an institution which will take care of these individuals...(Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

... Ahhh...That's it, mental illness is becoming more rampant, I mean a lot of people nowadays are suffering from this illness...so we should establish an institution which will take care of these individuals...

... strong support sap ag implement ng gantong batas ay kinakailangan natin para matulungan ang mga taong nakaka experience nito... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... strong support in the implementation for this law. We need to help one another to help this people who have an experience...

... uway mayroon na madekel den mambo, yung iba ahh yung nakulong na yung iba..narehab yun sa dun sa amas, general santos, pero hndi naman lahat ng nakulong ay gumagamit... (Bapa Rasul) (m4a_P6_Q3)

... Yes, we have a lot actually, some are now at jail, already detained, some are in rehab like in General santos and Amas, but not all detained are drug users...

Bapa Daud, who served as the only medical doctor in the town, stated that this individual should be treated with no judgment and should be accepted by the community. This was supported by Bapa Tahir who said that family members should not give up and widen their understanding for these people:

... lack of care and love by relatives, most especially the immediate family..another one, we should not treat this people as someone who is defective but instead we should not judgement, we should feel them that they are still accepted by the community... (Bapa Daud) (m4a_P9_Q3)

... lack of care and love by relatives, most especially the immediate family. Another one, we should not treat this people as someone who is defective but instead, we should not judgement, we should feel them that they are still accepted by the community...

... ahh ang intervention siguro dito bilang immediate na member ng family ng mga tao na may mental illness, yong wag natin sukuan yung pag intindi at paghahanap ng iba pang paraan kasi mayroon naman tayo mga institution na pweding makatulong kung paano natin eto bigyan ng solution, hindi kayang solusyonan sa level natin na immediate na relatives... (Bapa Tahir) (m4a_P7_Q3)

... ahh intervention I think, as an immediate family member, of a person having mental illness, we should not give up on them,

understanding, and to look for ways. We have also institution that can help these people to give solution which cannot be performed in the level of immediate family...

Table 4. Major Themes and Core Ideas on Insights that Muslim community can share regarding the experiences with people having mental illness

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Lack of strong spiritual foundation and faith in Allah	People become mentally ill because it is the will of Allah It is because of disobedience to Allah; lack of faith in Allah A form of punishment for not visiting the Mosque and pray Based on culture, lack of spiritual faith can cause illness If there is no strong faith in God, bad spirit will enter the body No illness can't be cured without God's intervention Jinns, like shaitan possesses those who do not pray to God Too much stress from the environment can cause mental illness Brought about by physical/biological alterations and lifestyle Acquired mental illness from genes and hereditary factors
Major stress and trauma in life	Drug usually is the reason, mind destroyed by drug abuse Being bombarded with problems and stress causes mental illness Displacement from the society Too much loneliness may develop mental illness They should be treated right away They should be treated with medication or Taligamot
Lack of appropriate treatment and mental health professionals	There is no doctor at the health center, only a midwife There are modern and scientific ways to treat the illness Treatment should be done to bring back their mindful sense Intervention by medical practitioners is necessary Individuals with mental illness should be brought to a psychiatrist Medicine is costly; treatment cannot be sustained Not enough treatment facilities for mentally ill people Institutions to care for the mentally ill should be established
Lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support	There is lack of support from significant family members They have no one to lean on in terms of problematic situation Lack of love and care by relatives compounds their situation The government should support the treatment for these people Community needs to extend help/assistance to these people Appropriate solution is rehabilitation in the case of drug use

Relevant Experiences of Maguindanaon Community on People with Mental Illness in the Mainstream

Based on the results, four main (4) themes were drawn from the experiences of Maguindanaon community among people having mental illness in the mainstream. These themes were all drawn from core ideas based on the cut down statements of the participants. These were the following: risk of aggression and violence, Unusual and off the wall actuations, wretchedness and abject despondency, and facts and myths on mental illness.

Risk of Aggression and Violence. This theme derived from the responses of the participants based on their point of view. Most of the participants agreed that people having mental illness in the mainstream would not hesitate to hurt anyone, they are aggressive and easily get anger, punches people, throw anything gets in hand and violent even with the family members. This finding confirms the study of Mark R. Seper (2011) who is a professor of Hofstra University under Clinical Psychology doctorate program. According to Seper, on his study on Aggression in Schizophrenia, one of the major communities and public concerns is the act of aggression committed by this individual having mental illness in the mainstream. This in fact affects not just the individual itself but also the families, clinicians and the community in large. Fuller Torrey (2011) who is the Associate Director of Research at the Stanley Medical Research Institute scrutinizes stigma brought about by the condition of this individual and its relationship to aggression, taking issue with gaps in the nation's mental health system that fails to adequately treat mentally ill individual which in turn increases risks of aggression and violence. According to Torrey (2011), failure to treat people with mental illness in fact is a major predictor of risk of aggression and violence among individual living in the community. He also added that the perceived dangerousness among individual having mental illness is treacherous and the stigma is one of the major hindrances today especially in terms of treatment (Barlati et. Al., 2019; Torrey, 2011).

Unusual and off the wall actuations. This theme was drawn from the participants own experiences and views among these individuals which are considered bizarre but not necessarily causes harm. Following core ideas extracted from the participants, these includes being restless, keeps on talking to oneself excessively, keeps on whispering, cannot sleep and keeps on walking around in the middle of the night, they feel anxious and suspicious. This theme was supported by American Psychiatric Association (2013). Symptoms of unusual behavior are notable among individual having mental illness such as schizophrenia. Specifically, these symptoms are considered positive such as hallucinations, delusions, thought disorder and disorganized speech, behavioral disorganization or catatonia which are unusual, negative such as inability to feel emotions with flattening of affect, inability to experience pleasure or anhedonia, loss of interest in social relationships, lack of motivation and reduction of impairment of speech which are considered off-the-wall actuations (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Wretchedness and Abject Despondency. The second theme adheres the idea that people having mental illness experience unfortunate state such as enormously unhappiness, extreme hopelessness and helplessness which affects their perception and entire self. Based on the experiences of most participants, they emphasized that people having mental illness are distressed, mournful, no more proper hygiene, they become drug dependent, cannot understand flow of conversation and always out of topic; they are malnourished, Goes around naked, Troubled sleeping, overthinking, and the worst is they are having suicidal tendencies. These observations capture the symptoms of hopelessness, helplessness of people having mental illness specifically Major Depression. Miserable and Negative feelings such as hopelessness are experienced by people having depression. This supported by the by American Psychiatric Association (2013). The APA (2013) depressive symptoms including depressed mood, inability to feel pleasure, trouble in sleeping, appetite disturbances, feeling of fatigue, feeling worthless and excessive guilt, Diminished ability to think or concentrate, or indecisiveness, nearly every day, Recurrent thoughts of death, recurrent suicidal ideation without a specific plan, or a suicide attempt or a specific plan for committing suicide. These symptoms cause impairment in everyday functioning on an individual in social, occupational, or other important areas (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Facts and myths on mental illness. The researcher found out that Maguindanaon community's understanding on mental illness has both factual and mythical components. These Facts and myths were derived from participants own views and experiences on people having mental illness. For factual component, most of the participants agreed that mental illness was cause by genetic predisposition, drug addiction, and traumatic experiences, while mythical components are mental illness as a result of disobedience to Allah, excessive headache, and Jinn / Satan and Deping possession. This finding corroborate the study of Tzeferakos and Douzenis (2017) who stated that some Muslims has advanced views on mental illness while while in some others, the practice includes cautery, exorcism, and even physical violence.

It was further described that in explaining the nomenclature, there are three basic trends, the Organic approach which are based on biology and pathophysiological explanation, the Psychological component which inspects and examines the intrapsychic conflicts; and lastly, the Magical or Sacred component which explains insanity as caused by supernatural or divine scope (Tzeferakos and Douzenis, 2017). Examining the core ideas of the theme drug addiction and genetic disposition will fall under biology and pathophysiological component, traumatic and stressful experiences will fall under psychological components and disobedience to Allah, excessive headache, and Jinn / Satan and Deping possession under the supernatural and divine component (Tzeferakos and Douzenis, 2017).

In factual bases, contrary to the thoughts of Western societies that Muslims believe on mental illnesses are solely due to demons or bad spirit-related, it was in fact Muslim scholars such as Ibn Sina (1037) also known the founder of Modern Medicine, rejected such concept and viewed mental illnesses as conditions that has physiological bases (Sabry and Vohra, 2013). This notion was in fact seen during the interview conducted among Maguindanaon who expressed that mental health is caused by drug addiction, genetic predisposition, and traumatic life experiences.

Mythical bases on the other hand is supported by Last (2015) which according to him, Demonic possessions and existence of Jinn, and exorcism are part of Muslim culture. Possession pertains to a condition wherein triggered individual losses their control which believed to be caused by a supernatural power (Last, 2015). Jinn are considered a separated race that may come out into a various form. It is believed that it may causes physical unwellness and such emotion as sadness and anger. In addition, Jinns can be used to destroy marriages, may cause insanity and last long body pain (Abdussalam-Bali, 2004; Dein & Illaiee, 2013). Some manifestation of Jinn possession including bizzare or unusual behaviors (Khalifa & Hardie 2005; Ally & Laher, 2007; Alli, 2020). Another mythical exercise of Muslim is the traditional healing, where traditional healer such as derwish, shaykh or pir (It depends on geographical location), exercise several rituals to heal a people having mental illness. This model describes the illness or personal problems as a possession by spirit (jinn). The solution according to healer is to do exorcism, through reading Muslim bible (Quran), Sallah or prayers, music, performing a dance, and beating spirits, out of the person's body, which eventually freed the individual from wretchedness (Sorsdahl et. Al., 2011; Saged et al., 2018).

Maguindanaon community copings with the challenges on people having mental illness

This study reveals the different coping mechanisms of Maguindanaon community in dealing with people having mental illness in the mainstream. These includes strong faith in Allah, giving and seeking intervention and support, generosity of spirit, kindness and acceptance, and avoidance among this individual.

Strong faith in Allah. It was revealed that in any problems that the community is facing, they always seek Allah's intervention. This allows them to strengthen their own faith. In such problem as dealing with mental illness, most participants agreed that having a strong faith to Allah will help them to deliver from any problem such as mental illness. This was supported by Zeenah Adam (2016) and other authors who stated that for Muslim community, Islam is considered a comprehensive way of life that infuses or fills cognitive, affective, behavioral, and spiritual aspects of the self (Adam, 2016; Abu Raiya and Pargament, 2011). It is probable, also that when individual is confronted with problems such as dealing with people having an illness, the community considers religion a resource in managing their distress. Undeniably, previous researches indicated that the community engage religion as a coping mechanism in response to stress at high rates relative to other religious groups (Adam, 2016).

Giving and seeking intervention and support. Another coping mechanism emerges from the participants interview was themed Giving and seeking intervention and support which suggested that in dealing with people having mental illness, the Muslim community relies on giving this individual some forms of treatment from religious point of view to modern ways of treatment. This should be accompanied by the support from other significant relatives of this individual. The notable treatment so far is by bringing this individual to a faith healer such as Babo Pakong since there were no mental health facilities or professionals available in the community. In contrast to the claim of previous researcher which found that many Muslims are hesitant to seek help from the mental health professionals due to the differences in their beliefs and lack of understating (Sabry and Vohra, 2013). Muslim Maguindanaons are not hesitant in seeking treatment and support in fact, they want to have institution that will cater these individuals.

In addition to seeking treatment, Maguindanaon community deals with this individual by giving support and taking care of them especially members of the family. This coping mechanism was supported by Waller et al. (2018) which stated that, emotional and social support are some of the coping mechanisms of family having mentally ill member. Similarly, Borg and Davidson's (2008) found out that families lend money, they give housing and undertake household chores among family member with mental illness (Waller, Reupert, Ward, McCormick, & Kid, 2018).

Generosity of spirits. This theme was drawn from the participant's response such as they take care of this individual, give them foods to eat, provide a shelter and showing some kindness and mercy. This coping mechanism was supported by Tanaka, Tuliao, Tanaka, Yamashita & Matsuo (2018) who stated that Bayanihan spirit, a traditional concept of community unity, relieved the negative influences of stigma on people with mental health problems or PMHP. It was not rare that community people gave food or rented a house free to PMHP and their family who had little income. Helping one another in a time of need was inherent in their lives, called Bayanihan in Tagalog (Tanaka, Tuliao, Tanaka, Yamashita & Matsuo, 2018).

Kindness and acceptance. The result of the study suggested that, Muslim community shows kindness and total acceptance among this individual in the mainstream. Contrary to the previous researches, Muslims community in Maguindanao shows that they are very careful in terms of dealing with this individual. In fact, most participants stated that they are accepted and do not considered outcast in the community. This theme contradicts to the idea of stigma associated by mental illness, which according to Jones and Corrigan (2012), most of Muslim communities, often perceived as a monolithic group, negatively stereotyped and subjected to significant interpersonal and structural discrimination especially when it comes to mental illness issue. Instead of discriminating this individual, the Maguindanaon community showed their support and kindness towards this individual.

Avoidance. This theme derived from the experience of Maguindanaon community among people with mental illness in the mainstream. The result suggested that some participants avoid this individual due to perceived possible harm brought about by this people. This was supported by previous researchers who concluded that lay people tend to view patient with mental disorder (specifically schizophrenia) as violent and thus, desire to maintain social distance are common (Van Dorm et al., 2005 ;Jones and Corrigan, 2012; Hankir, Pendegast, Carrick, Zaman, 2017).

Insights of Maguindanaon Community on their experience among People Having Mental Illness

Based on the results, four main (4) themes were drawn from the Insights the community can share on their experience among people having mental illness in the mainstream. These themes were all drawn from core ideas based on the responses on the participants. These are the following: Lack of Strong Spiritual Foundation and Faith to Allah, Major Stress and Trauma in Life, Lack of Appropriate Treatment and Mental Health Professionals, and Lack of Treatment Facilities and All Kinds of Support.

Lack of strong spiritual foundation and faith in Allah. This theme was drawn from the insights of most participants who believed that mental illness was brought about by weak spiritual foundation and faith in Allah. Thus, mental illness serves as punishment and it is all will of Allah. this theme was supported by Ameera AlGhafri (2019) who stated that, in our culturally- driven societies, Muslim community seem to think that with lack of faith causes person to develop mental health problems. She added that our society views people with mental health issue as sinners or a disgrace to society. Her colleague conducted a survey research addressing the community's misconception of "lack of religion leads to depression". Surprisingly, 60% of the Muslim respondents agreed to the idea. This survey offers strong evidence that misconception is present in the society which is important to be addressed (AlGhafri, 2019).

Major stress and trauma in life. Another theme emerged from the insights among Muslim community suggested that mental illness stems stress and trauma experience brought about by excessive problems the individual is facing. Furthermore, this stress and trauma has its origin on person's genes, and it is believed to be inherited according to Muslim participants. This is supported by 'diathesis

stress model' first used by Paul Meehl in 1960 which suggested that in development of mental illness, two contributing factors interplay. These are the diathesis or vulnerability of an individual in such illness which originated from individuals' genes and stress is the adverse life-events which are too difficult to handle into mental health problems (Meehl, 1960). This theme also is supported by reciprocal gene-environment model which hypothesized that people with a genetic disposition tend to create environmental risk factors that promote disorders (Barlow and Durand, 2012). This is true to participants where they emphasized that individual who experienced loneliness and stress tends to engage themselves into drugs. This stress again has biological or physiological origin.

Lack of appropriate treatment and Mental Health Professionals. This emerging theme was drawn from participants insights that appropriate solution especially among people with mental illness as a result of drug addiction is rehabilitation. That proper medication should administer to address the problem in the community. Lack of appropriate treatment and mental health professionals hinders the community from doing what is supposed to do this individual. Professional such as psychiatrist are some of the mentioned profession which according to participants can help them to address the problem. Since there were not enough mental health professionals, the community are forced to seek an intervention among faith healers such as Babo Pakong, look for a midwife which are available in the community, or just leave this individual without any intervention. These responses of the community were supported by (Lally et al, 2019) on their recent study on National information on mental health services in the Philippines which specifies that there are substantial gaps and inconsistencies in the delivery of mental healthcare in the country (Lally et al, 2019).

The Mental Health Act legislation provides a platform for the delivery of comprehensive and integrated mental health services in the country. Unfortunately, there many issues in the provision of accessible and affordable mental healthcare. In fact, in every 80, 000 Filipinos, there were only one doctor available according to world health organization (WHO, 2012) and department of health (DOH, 2012). Some of the reason of this scarcity is the emigration of mental health practitioner to other countries. This deficiency is magnified in psychiatry where, nationally, there are a little over 500 psychiatrists in practice. In terms of the ratio, there were two (2) to three (3) mental health workers in every 100, 000 population (Lally et al, 2019). In addition, Data shows that there are 0.52 psychiatrists (Isaac et al, 2018) and 0.07 psychologists per 100 000 inhabitants, and 0.49 mental health nurses per 100 000 of the population (a reduction from 0.72 per 100 000 in 2011) (WHO, 2014).

In terms of appropriate treatment and medication, there are only meager data on prescription rates and the use of psychotropic medications in treating mental illness. According to Lally and associates (2019), the World Health Organization- Health Survey reveals that only a third of people with a diagnosis of schizophrenia were receiving treatment or screening. Mental healthcare in the Philippines faces challenges such as under investment, lack of mental health professionals and underdeveloped community mental health services. While the recent Mental Health Act legislation has provided a legal framework for the delivery of comprehensive mental health services, economic restrictions should be considered to allow the community to access appropriate care when needed. Increased investment is urgently needed to improve the training and recruitment of psychiatrists, nurses, psychologists, social workers and other mental health professions, especially the huge numbers of skilled professionals continue to relocate in other countries (Lally, Tully and Samaniego, 2019).

Lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support. The last theme refers to the insights of the Muslim community. Concern by most are the lack of facilities available in the community. Just like the lack of mental health professional, the community agreed that there must be a treatment center among individual having mental illness in the mainstream. In addition to that, all kinds of support should also be established in order for the patients to recover immediately. This theme was supported by the researchers Walaa Sabry and Adarsh Vohra (2013) who stated that with the significant growth of the Muslim population all over the world, there exists a corresponding increase in the need for mental health services that suit this group of patients (Walaa M. Sabry and Adarsh Vohra (2013).

Implication for Practice

This study was set out to answer a series of related research questions. In this section, the researcher presented the summary of findings and implications for current and future practice.

Based on the results drawn from most participants experience, people suffering from mental illness who are in the mainstream Muslim community are capable of hurting anyone even his family member because of aggressive and violent behavior. Participants confirmed that most of these individuals gets easily angered and do not hesitate to hurt other especially when mistreated. Unusual and off the wall actuation such as walking in the middle of the night, talking to oneself, talking excessively, laughing alone, running, keeps picking trashes, act and does weird things are also observed by the Maguindanaon community.

In addition, wretchedness and abject despondency was also observed among these individuals. Such experience are the suicidal tendencies, feeling of distress, mournful and lonely, goes around naked, no proper hygiene, unkept hair, engaging oneself to drugs and some other symptoms of helplessness, hopelessness and worthlessness experience by these individuals was validated by the community based on their observation and experience. Muslim community's belief on mental illness has both mythical and factual bases which are considered culturally embedded to them which might affect the progression of the illness among this individual.

Although the community wants to admit them to a mental hospital or in a treatment center which caters and facilitates suffering from any mental illnesses, perceived problems including the lack of any treatment facilities, costly medications, and even lack of mental health professionals are seen to be some of the hindrances.

Thus, mental health professionals such as psychologists and psychiatrists, social workers, guidance counselors, psychiatric nurses, psychometricians, educators and other related fields should coordinate with both national, local and non-government organization to strengthen the liaison between mental health care and local communities. This will be done by providing a local treatment facility with at least one mental health practitioner to facilitate these individuals, and to provide low cost medicines. To the Muslim community, psychoeducation should be conducted to educate the community on solely factual bases of mental illness and how they can contribute to the development of the program and people with mental illness in the mainstream to recover gradually. Mental health services should focus on prevention, recovery, rehabilitation and after-care program among individual with mental illnesses. The research participants believed that the provision of social and well-being support from our concerned parties would help to safeguard the mental wellness of the community in general. Below are the implication of practice for each them:

On the risk of aggression and violence, Maguindanaon community describes people having mental illness in the mainstream who gets easily anger, punches people, run after people, throws anything gets in hand, and capable of hurting anyone even his family member because of aggressive and violent behavior. This implies that people suffering from mental illness in the mainstream are dangerous to the community where this individual resides. These threats brought about by this individual should be addressed by bringing them into an mental health institution which will facilitates their medication and therapy to avoid aggressive and violent behavior. Also, mental health practitioner may conduct psychoeducation among Muslim community to provide an awareness on how to predict, deal and avoid the occurrence of such violence and aggression.

On the Unusual and off the wall actuations, most participants agreed that people who are suffering from mental illness shows bizarre behavior, this is unusual and off the wall actuations which the community considered “weird stuff”. Such unusual behavior including walking in the middle of the night, keeps on punching, restlessness, laughing alone implies that this individual suffering from mental illness experience dissociation which contributes to the community’s perceived challenges and threats since they are unpredictable. Among the individual suffering from mental illness, this implies the problem of progression of the mental illness which affect the individual functioning not just in terms of personal but also on social aspect which should immediately be addressed by concerned individual such as local government unit personnel and mental health professionals to help them manage the symptoms brought about by the illness.

On the wretchedness and abject despondency, most participants agreed that people with mental illness in the mainstream are lonely, mournful, have troubled in sleeping, they overthink, and are distressed with no proper hygiene. This implies that people suffering from mental illness experience hopelessness, helplessness, and worthlessness which affects their daily functioning like personal (no proper hygiene, goes around naked), social (separation from the husband, blaming parents) and other areas in functioning which indicates the need for awareness seminar pertaining to the individual mental health issues particularly on the prevention and development of depression. Early detection of depressive symptoms enables the community or family of a person suffering from depression to monitor and support these individuals. In addition, this will enables the community to become aware of the nature and causes of depression.

On the facts and myths on mental illness, Maguindanaon community believed that mental illness is caused by drug addiction, traumatic or stressful life experiences, and even has genetic predisposition which implies that Muslim community in Maguindanaon has factual understanding on what mental illness is. On the other hand, there are some culturally embedded belief that mental illness is brought about by the punishment of Allah (God), Jinn/Satan, Deping possession and excessive headache which are considered myths at least in the practice of modern science. This implies that Muslim local community needs psychoeducation which should focus on biological, psychological and sociological explanation on the cause and development of mental illness. On the other hand, integrating religious belief in designing therapeutic intervention may also be considered by mental health professionals to maximize the effects of therapy among these individuals.

On Strong faith in Allah, most Maguindanaon participants agreed that to conquer one’s own problem, one must submitted himself to Allah, having a strong foundation to God according to them will help someone to be delivered from any kinds of illness including mental illness. In psychological perspective, this implies religion plays role on mental wellness among the community. Thus, the need for integrative approach in Muslim mental health should be addressed not only focusing on the biopsychosocial perspective but in addition, by integrating spiritual aspect of the community.

On giving and seeking intervention and support, most of the Muslim participants help the individual suffering from mental illness by helping them seeks intervention such as Taligamot (Fatih healers) or Imam (Ustadz), support from the relatives was also seen mechanism in coping with people having mental illness. This implies that Muslim community are open to any intervention and support that can help people with mental illness in their mainstream. This also suggested of the less stigmatizing behavior of the Muslim community among people suffering from mental illness. The need for biopsychosocial & spiritual treatment integration is urgently needed.

On generosity of spirit, Muslim participants shows kindness and mercy among individual having mental illness in the mainstream, this is through providing shelters, giving foods, and even taking care of them. This implies that Muslim community do not stereotype this individual as someone who is different instead, they are doing their part to help these people even in a simple manner. The case of Dutin is a good illustration of how Muslim community treated people suffering from mental illness as someone who is not different and defective.

On kindness and acceptance, most participants agreed that people with mental illness are not considered outcast in the society, they make them believe that they are belong and accepted, the community will not give up on them and continue to understand this individual. This suggested and implies that Muslim community are open to this individual and in fact shows their unconditional regard with this people showing support to recover from the illness.

On avoidance, participants avoided people with mental illness for possible threat. On the other hand, this action of avoidance shows someone's discriminative behavior towards people suffering from mental illness. This avoidance is for safety purposes. This theme implies that there is still discrimination among this individual not solely because of their condition in general but on the perceived possible threat brought about by their conditions. Thus, the need for mental health awareness program should be implemented to educate the community on the different common classification of mental illness especially the harmful versus the nonharmful one. In addition, stigma on mental illness should also be part of the psychoeducation addressing the negative impact of stereotyping and discrimination.

On lack of spiritual foundation to and faith in Allah, Muslim participants asserted that lack of strong spiritual foundation and faith to Allah was said to be the cause of mental illness. Lack of spiritual foundation and faith to Allah allows bad spirits to enter human body which eventually turns into a mental illness. This serves as punishment and will of Allah because of not visiting Mosque or reading Qur'an. Thus, to heal this individual, they must submit themselves to Allah and serve the God. This implies that Muslim community are tied with religious dogma which are part already of their lifestyle. Thus, spiritual aspect (religion) should be integrated to the intervention program design to help people with mental illness recover. In addition, the need to educate the community on mental illness is needed to address the current issues especially on views on mental illness.

On major stress and trauma in life, Muslim community shared that one of the major causes of the development of mental illness is due to a stress and trauma brought about by the environment. This stress and trauma act as triggering factor originated from individuals' genes which are considered predisposition of this individuals according to most participants. Predisposition to stress are then triggered by individual's lifestyle such as engaging oneself to drugs, displacement in the society and too much loneliness due to serious life problems. This implies that Muslim community in Maguindanao has wide understanding on what mental illness is and how it is developed. The need to conduct seminar focusing on resiliency is needed to establish the community's coping mechanism with stress and trauma in life.

On lack of appropriate treatment and mental health professionals, the community are awareness on the possible benefits of introducing these individuals on some medications and appropriate intervention (such as psychotherapy) of a mental health professional. Obviously, the problem is the lack of this appropriate treatment and even professional to treat this individual. The community in general have no choice but to look for a faith healer or Imam serves as last resort since no one appropriate professional is available to help this individual. This implies the need to have mental health professionals such as psychologists, psychiatrists, counselors, psychiatric nurses, social workers and some other allied profession to work out on this issue especially, the mental health law is now implementing the mental health in all aspects including local community.

On lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support, accompanied by the lack of appropriate professional is also the lack of treatment facilities and all kinds of support among these individuals. Most of the participants in Muslim local community in Maguindanao suggested the need to treatment facilities that will cater this individual especially they are aggressive and violent at times. Also, lack of social support, significant others and costly medication as seen problem they encountered. Thus, the community wants to have at least a treatment center where all supports, medication are all available. This implies the need to focus on addressing problem on mental health particularly by establishing mental health institution which caters the individual suffering from mental illness in the mainstream. This will help the community to widen the understanding on mental illness which are just like physical illness which requires admission to the hospitals.

Implication for Future Research

This study is open for chances for future research and several directions for future researchers and clinical work. In terms methodology, the future researchers should focus on doing survey quantifying the stigma associated by mental illness in Muslim community in Philippine context. This will serve better understanding on how Muslim community in general views and perceives people having mental illness in the mainstream considering their beliefs and practices. Studies involving Filipino Muslim community are very few and limited, considering the role of culture and other factors in viewing mental illness seems to be very interesting.

Furthermore, the study is limited to the Maguindanaon ethnolinguistic group only. Future researchers may conduct and replicate the study by applying the same qualitative method of investigation to various Muslim ethnolinguistic group located in Mindanao and some other parts of the country. Through this, findings of this study maybe validated, confirmed and be able to somehow generalize the results to the entire Muslim community in the Philippine context.

Conclusions

Personally, the researcher adhere to this study primarily because he is Maguindanaon mental health advocate who personally experienced and witnessed people suffering from mental illness being discriminated in the community way back then. To unearth the experiences of fellow Muslims seems so fascinating considering that the community has poor mental health care which personally the

researcher wish to address. Upon interview, the researcher was given the chance to meet this individual suffering from mental illness in the mainstream which gave him the motivation to pursue the degree in clinical psychology to help not just these individuals but the community at large to widen their understanding on mental illness.

To all readers of this paper, this paper may serve as an instrument in helping the community and people suffering mental illness as part of the advocacy as mental health educator and a practitioner. Providing a supportive and understanding community should highly be practiced and observed to help these individuals in their recovery. Establishing a good community will served as prevention in developing such illness as we know, environment is a great contributing factor which might affect individual's mental health. Furthermore, the need for mental health professionals, appropriate medication and treatment facilities in all levels such national or local should be strengthen to facilitate the needs of these individuals.

Finally, the researcher is hopeful that through this study, Filipino community at large will appreciate the presence and help of all mental health professionals such as psychologists, psychiatrists, guidance counselors, psychometricians, and other allied professions.

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